

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY

B. TECH. (HONOURS): REGULATION - 2019

B.TECH. (HONOURS) SCHEME & SYLLABUS

**ELECTRONICS AND
COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING**

WITH

SCHEME OF TEACHING

III – VIII SEMESTER

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

College of Engineering & Technology

B. TECH (HONOURS) IN ELECTRONICS AND COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING

Basic Rules and Regulations of the Institution:

1. Classes will be from 9.00 AM to 4.30 PM on all working days
2. In the semester system, students have to be regular in academics from the day one and should follow the proper study plan throughout the course
3. Students must be time conscious and expected to be on the time to the theory and practical classes
4. 85% attendance is compulsory for appearing to semester exams
5. Student should avail leave only with prior information or in the case of acute emergency
6. Attending all the internal assessment tests (IA) is compulsory.
7. Students should obtain the minimum required IA marks and need to submit assignments and reports to appear for the final examinations
8. Students are expected to maintain a good academic culture and discipline in the class rooms, library, canteen, corridors, bus and hostels.
9. Indulging in Ragging is a punishable offence and strict action will be taken against those who are directly or indirectly involved
10. Srinivas University campus is 100% free from ragging
11. Usage of Mobile phones in the academic area is not allowed. Students can make use of lockers for keeping the same during the class hours.
12. All the faculty members are easily approachable and students are expected to use the opportunity for their academic development

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
College of Engineering and Technology

SCHEME OF TEACHING AND EXAMINATION 2019

B.TECH. (HONOURS) IN ELECTRONICS AND COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING

III SEMESTER

SL. No	Subject Code	Title	Teaching				Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	Self-Study / Practice	IA	Exam	Total	
1	19SMA31	Numerical Techniques and Integral Transforms	4	1	0	0	50	50	100	4
2	19SEC32	Analog Devices and Circuits	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
3	19SEC33	Digital System Design	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
4	19SEC34	Microprocessors & Embedded Systems	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
5	19SECL35	Analog Electronic Circuits Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
6	19SECL36	Digital System Design Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
7	19SECL37	Microprocessors Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
8	19SEC38	ESEP - Circuit Analysis, Simulation and Debugging	0	1	2	0	25	25	50	2
9	19SQA39	Part-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 1 (ESEP 1)	2	0	0	0	50	-	50	2
		Part-B: International Certification Course on Current Trends - 1	0	0	0	2	-	-	-	
Total Marks/Credits			18	05	08	02	425	375	800	26

SCHEME OF TEACHING AND EXAMINATION 2019
B.TECH. (HONOURS) IN ELECTRONICS AND COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING
IV Semester

SL. No	Subject Code	Title	Teaching				Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	Self-Study / Practice	IA	Exam	Total	
1	19SMA41	Probability theory and Statistical Methods	4	1	0	0	50	50	100	4
2	19SEC42	Design and Analysis of algorithms	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
3	19SEC43	EM Waves and Transmission	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
4	19SEC44	Principles of Communication	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
5	19SECL45	Analog Communication Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
6	19SECL46	ICs and Circuits Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
7	19SECL47	Algorithms and OOPs Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
8	19SEC48	ESEP- Introduction to Emerging Technologies	0	1	2	0	25	25	50	2
9	19SQA49	Part-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 2 (ESEP 2)	2	0	0	0	50	-	50	2
		Part-B: International Certification Course on Current Trends - 2	0	0	0	2	-	-	-	
Total Marks/Credits			18	05	08	02	425	375	800	26

SCHEME OF TEACHING AND EXAMINATION 2019
B.TECH. (HONOURS) IN ELECTRONICS AND COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING
V Semester

SL. No	Subject Code	Title	Teaching				Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	Self-Study / Practice	IA	Exam	Total	
1	19SEC51	Digital Signal Processing	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
2	19SEC52	Computer Networks	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
3	19SEC53X	Core-Elective -1	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
4	19SEC54X	Optional/Soft Elective	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
5	19SECL55	Signal Processing and EM Waves Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
6	19SECL56	Computer Networks Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
7	19SECL57	Hardware Description Languages Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
8	19SEC58	ESEP - MOOC	0	0	0	2	50	-	50	2
9	19SQA59	Part-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 3 (ESEP 3)	2	0	0	0	50	-	50	2
		Part-B: International Certification Course on Current Trends - 3	0	0	0	2	-	-	-	
Total Marks/Credits			18	03	06	04	450	350	800	26

Core Elective – 1		Optional/Soft Elective	
19SEC531	Instrumentation and Control	19SEC541	Operating System
19SEC532	Digital Control	19SEC542	Nano Electronics
19SEC533	Automotive Electronics	19SEC543	MEMS and Nano Technology
19SEC534	Medical Electronics	19SEC544	Real Time Systems
19SEC535	Aviation Electronics	19SEC545	Consumer Electronics

SCHEME OF TEACHING AND EXAMINATION 2019
B.TECH. (HONOURS) IN ELECTRONICS AND COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING
VI Semester

SL. No	Subject Code	Title	Teaching				Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	Self-Study / Practice	IA	Exam	Total	
1	19SEC61	Advanced Communication	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
2	19SEC62	VLSI Circuits	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
3	19SEC63X	Core-Elective -2	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
4	19SEC64X	Open Elective-1	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
5	19SECL65	Advanced Communication Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
6	19SECL66	VLSI Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
7	19SECL67	Image Processing Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
8	19SEC68	ESEP - Mini Project	0	0	0	4	50	-	50	2
9	19SQA69	Part-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 4 (ESEP 4)	2	0	0	0	50	-	50	2
		Part-B: International Certification Course on Current Trends - 4	0	0	0	2	-	-	-	
Total Marks/Credits			18	03	06	06	450	350	800	26

Core Elective – 2		Open Elective -1	
19SEC631	Digital Image Processing	19SEC641	Cryptography and Network Security
19SEC632	IOT Technology & Applications	19SEC642	Optical Fiber and Networks
19SEC633	MSP 430 Microcontrollers		
19SEC634	Machine Learning		

BoS Chairman

Dean

SCHEME OF TEACHING AND EXAMINATION 2019
B.TECH. (HONOURS) IN ELECTRONICS AND COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING
VII Semester

SL. No	Subject Code	Title	Teaching				Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	Self-Study / Practice	IA	Exam	Total	
1	19SEC71	Power Electronics	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
2	19SEC72X	Core Elective –3	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
3	19SEC73X	Core Elective – 4	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
4	19SEC74X	Open Elective – 2	4	0	0	0	50	50	100	4
5	19SECL75	Data Communication Lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
6	19SECL76	Power Electronics lab	0	1	2	0	50	50	100	2
7	19SECL77	Project Phase I	0	0	2	2	50	50	100	2
8	19SEC78	ESEP – MOOC	0	0	0	2	50	-	50	2
9	19SQA79	ESEP - Employability Skill Enhancement Programme - Patent Filing & IPR	2	0	0	0	50	-	50	2
Total Marks/Credits			18	02	06	04	450	350	800	26

Core Elective – 3		Core Elective – 4		Open Elective -2	
19SEC721	Data Acquisition & PLC	19SEC731	Pattern Recognition	19SEC741	DSP Algorithms and Architecture
19SEC722	Digital Switching Systems	19SEC732	Computer Vision	19SEC742	Object Oriented Programming in C++
19SEC723	Medical Electronics	19SEC733	Multimedia Communication	19SEC743	Advanced JAVA Programming
19SEC724	Introduction to NEMS	19SEC734	Introduction to MEMS	19SEC744	Database Management Systems
				19SEC745	Internet of Things

SCHEME OF TEACHING AND EXAMINATION 2019
B.TECH. (HONOURS) IN ELECTRONICS AND COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING
VIII Semester

SL. No	Subject Code	Title	Teaching				Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	Self-Study / Practice	IA	Exam	Total	
1	19SEC81	Technical Seminar	0	0	0	4	100	0	100	2
2	19SEC82	Internship	0	0	0	4	50	50	100	3
3	19SEC83	Project Work (With Option of Patent Application)	0	0	24	0	100	100	200	13
		Total Marks/Credits	0	0	24	08	250	150	400	18

BoS Chairman

Dean

NUMERICAL TECHNIQUES AND INTEGRAL TRANSFORMS

Subject Code	19SMA31	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 1(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of this course are to introduce students to the mostly used analytical and numerical methods in the different engineering fields by making them to learn Fourier series, Fourier transforms, z-transforms and numerical methods to solve ordinary differential equations.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

- CO1: Know the use of periodic signals and Fourier series to analyze circuits and system communications.
- CO2: Explain the general linear system theory for continuous-time signals and digital signal processing using the Fourier Transform and Employ appropriate numerical methods to solve algebraic and transcendental equations
- CO3: Solve first order ordinary differential equations arising in flow problems
- CO4: Using single step and multistep numerical methods.
- CO5: Apply the concept of Z- transform to engineering problems.

MODULE 1

Fourier Series: Periodic functions, Dirichlet's condition, Fourier Series of periodic functions with period 2π and with arbitrary period $2c$. Half range Fourier Series, practical harmonic analysis-Illustrative examples from engineering field.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Fourier Transform: Infinite Fourier transforms, Fourier sine and cosine transforms. Inverse Fourier transforms, Problems. Numerical Methods: Numerical solution of algebraic and transcendental equations by Regula-Falsi Method and Newton-Raphson method

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Numerical solution of ordinary differential equations: Numerical solution of simultaneous first order ordinary differential equation and first degree, Taylor's series method, Modified Euler's method, Runge kutta method of fourth order. Milne's and Adam's bash forth predictor and creditor method.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Numerical solution of second order ordinary differential equations: Numerical solution of simultaneous differential equation, Numerical solution of second order ordinary differential equations, Runge-Kutta method and Milne's method. (No derivations of formulae).

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Difference equations and Z-transforms: Difference equations, basic definition, z-transform-definition, standard z-transforms, damping and shifting rules, initial value and final value theorems (without proof) and problems. Inverse z-transform-problems and applications to solve difference equations.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

INTERNAL MARKS DISTRIBUTION:

3 Internals Assessment (IA) Tests are conducted for 20 marks each and it will be reduced to 40 marks. Continuous Internal Evaluation (CIE): 5 marks. (Seminars, Quiz, Surprise Test, Assignments). Attendance: 5 marks.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 1 Marks x 10 = 10 Marks
PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from eachModule. 08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. E. Kreyszig: Advanced Engineering Mathematics, John Wiley & Sons, 10th Ed.(Reprint), 2017.
2. B.S. Grewal: Higher Engineering Mathematics, Khanna Publishers, 44th Ed., 2017.
3. Srimanta Pal & Subobh C Bhunia: "Engineering Mathematics", Oxford University Press, 3rd Reprint, 2016.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. C. Ray Wylie, Louis C. Barrett: "Advanced Engineering Mathematics", 6th Edition, 2. McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1995.
2. S. S. Sastry: "Introductory Methods of Numerical Analysis", 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010
3. B.V. Ramana: "Higher Engineering Mathematics" 11th Edition, Tata \ McGraw-Hill, 2010.
4. N. P. Bali and Manish Goyal, "A Text Book of Engineering Mathematics", Laxmi Publications. Latest edition, 2014.
5. Chandrika Prasad and Reena Garg "Advanced Engineerig mathematics, Latest edition, Khanna Publishing, 2018.

ANALOG DEVICES AND CIRCUITS

Subject Code	19SEC32	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Understand the construction and characteristics of JFETs and MOSFETs and differentiate with BJT
- Study Special Devices like UJT and Thyristors, Photo transistors.
- Analysis of Amplifier Circuits.
- Demonstrate and Analyze Operational Amplifier circuits and their applications

COURSE OUTCOMES:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Knowledge in BJT and FET Biasing and stabilization

CO2: Concepts of Amplifiers, feedback system

CO3: Working and application of Operational amplifier

MODULE 1

BJT Biasing Modeling: BJT Biasing and Q Point Stabilization. Field Effect Transistors Basics: Differences between JFETs and MOSFETs Basic MOSFET: Depletion and Enhancement MOSFET structure, Operation, Current-Voltage Characteristics. MOSFET Biasing. MOSFET Amplifier configuration: Basic configurations. UJT and Thyristors: Fundamentals of UJT, Diac, Triac, SCR Optoelectronic Devices

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Frequency response of amplifiers. Transistor models. T and Pi Models. h-parameter model of amplifiers. h-parameter model of BJT amplifiers. Analysis of different BJT amplifier configurations using h-parameters. Small signal response of FET amplifiers. Low-frequency response of BJT amplifiers. Low-frequency response of FET amplifiers. Cascading amplifiers. Darlington amplifiers. Cascode amplifiers. Effect of cascading amplifier cascades on the overall frequency response.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Feedback Amplifier: General feedback structure, Properties of negative feedback, Basic feedback topologies, The series-shunt, series-series, shunt-shunt and shunt-series amplifiers (Qualitative analysis). Positive Feedback, Barkhausen Criteria Oscillators. Power Amplifiers:

Introduction, Classification, Class A operation, Transfer Characteristics, Signal Waveforms, Power Dissipation, Power Conversion efficiency, Transformer Coupled Power Amplifiers, Class B transformer coupled amplifier, Class B output stage, Transfer Characteristics, Power Dissipation, Power Conversion efficiency, Class AB – Operation, Class C tuned Amplifier.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Operational Amplifier Fundamentals: Basic Op-amp circuit, Op-Amp parameters – Input and output voltage, CMRR and PSRR, offset voltages and currents, Input and output impedances, Slew rate and Frequency limitations. Op-Amp with Negative Feedback and general applications Inverting and Non inverting Amplifiers DC and AC Amplifiers, Summing, Scaling and Averaging Amplifiers, Instrumentation amplifier. Differentiating Circuit, Integrator Circuit

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 5

OP-Amp Applications: Voltage sources, current sources and current sinks, current amplifiers, precision rectifiers, Clippers, Clampers, Peak detectors, Sample and hold circuits, V to I and I to V converters, Comparators, Zero Crossing Detector, Schmitt trigger. Oscillators: Phase shift oscillator, Wein bridge oscillator, Monostable and astable multivibrator, inverting Schmitt trigger. Active Filters: First and second order Butterworth filters and its response (LP, HP, BP, BE).

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

INTERNAL MARKS DISTRIBUTION:

3 Internals Assessment (IA) Tests are conducted for 20 marks each and it will be reduced to 40 marks. Continuous Internal Evaluation (CIE): 5 marks. (Seminars, Quiz, Surprise Test, Assignments). Attendance: 5 marks.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 1 Marks x 10 = 10 Marks PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from eachModule. 08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Fundamentals of Data Structures in C - Ellis Horowitz and Sartaj Sahni, 2nd edition, Universities Press,2014
2. Data Structures - Seymour Lipschutz, Schaum's Outlines, Revised 1st edition, McGraw Hill,2014

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Data Structures: A Pseudo-code approach with C - Gilberg & Forouzan, 2nd edition, Cengage Learning, 2014.
2. Data Structures using C, Reema Thareja, 3rd edition Oxford press, 2012.
3. An Introduction to Data Structures with Applications- Jean-Paul Tremblay & Paul G. Sorenson, 2nd Edition, McGraw Hill, 2013.
4. Data Structures using C - A M Tenenbaum, PHI, 1989. 5. Data Structures and Program Design in C - Robert Kruse, 2nd edition, PHI, 1996.

DIGITAL SYSTEM DESIGN

Subject Code	19SEC33	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Describe, Illustrate and Analyze Combinational Logic circuits, Simplification of Algebraic Equations using Karnaugh Maps and QuineMcClusky Techniques.
- Describe and Design Decoders, Encoders, Digital multiplexers, Adders and Subtractors, Binary comparators, Latches and Master-Slave Flip-Flops.
- Describe, Design and Analyze Synchronous and Asynchronous Sequential
- Explain and design registers and Counters, A/D and D/A converters.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Design and analyze digital circuits using TTL/CMOS ICs.

CO2: Simplify digital circuits using Karnaugh Map, POS and Quine-McClusky Methods

CO3: Explain Gates and flipflops and make use in designing different data processing circuits, registers and counters and compare the types.

CO4: Develop simple HDL programs

CO5: Explain the basic principles of A/D and D/A conversion circuits and develop the same.

MODULE 1

Logic Families : TTL NAND gate, Specifications, Noise margin, Propagation delay, fan-in, fan-out, Tristate TTL, ECL. CMOS families, CMOS Characteristics, and their interfacing, TTL-to-CMOS Interface, CMOS-to-TTL Interface. The Basic Gates: Review of Basic Logic gates, Positive and Negative Logic, Introduction to HDL.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Combinational Logic Circuits: Sum-of-Products Method, Truth Table to Karnaugh Map, Pairs Quads, and Octets, Karnaugh Simplifications, Don't-care Conditions, Product-of-sums Method, Product-of-sums simplifications, Simplification by Quine-McClusky Method, Hazards and Hazard covers, HDL Implementation Models.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Data-Processing Circuits: Multiplexers, Demultiplexers, 1-of-16 Decoder, BCD to Decimal Decoders, Seven Segment Decoders, Encoders, Exclusive-OR Gates, Parity Generators and Checkers, Magnitude Comparator, Programmable Array Logic, Programmable Logic Arrays, HDL Implementation of Data Processing Circuits. Arithmetic Building Blocks, Arithmetic Logic Unit Flip- Flops: RS Flip-Flops, Gated Flip-Flops, Edge-triggered RS FLIP-FLOP, Edge-triggered D FLIP-FLOPs, Edge-triggered JK FLIPFLOPs.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Flip- Flops: FLIP-FLOP Timing, JK Master-slave FLIP-FLOP, Switch Contact Bounce Circuits, Various Representation of FLIP-FLOPs, HDL Implementation of FLIP-FLOP. Registers: Types of Registers, Serial In - Serial Out, Serial In - Parallel out, Parallel In - Serial Out, Parallel In - Parallel Out, Universal Shift Register, Applications of Shift Registers, Register implementation in HDL. Counters: Asynchronous Counters, Decoding Gates, Synchronous Counters, Changing the Counter Modulus.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Counters: Decade Counters, Presetable Counters, Counter Design as a Synthesis problem, A Digital Clock, Counter Design using HDL. D/A Conversion and A/D Conversion: Variable, Resistor Networks, Binary Ladders, D/A Converters, D/A Accuracy and Resolution, A/D Converter-Simultaneous Conversion, A/D Converter-Counter Method, Continuous A/D Conversion, A/D Techniques, Dual-slope A/D Conversion, A/D Accuracy and Resolution.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

INTERNAL MARKS DISTRIBUTION:

3 Internals Assessment (IA) Tests are conducted for 20 marks each and it will be reduced to 40 marks. Continuous Internal Evaluation (CIE): 5 marks. (Seminars, Quiz, Surprise Test, Assignments). Attendance: 5 marks.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 1 Marks x 10 = 10Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from eachModule. 08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. A.K Maini, Varsha Agarwal, Electronic Devices and Circuit,1st Edition, Wiley 2011
2. A.P Malvino, Bates D, Electronic Principles,8th Edition, MGH,2016
3. Donald P Leach, Albert Paul Malvino & Goutam Saha: Digital Principles and Applications, 8th Edition, Tata McGraw Hill, 2015

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. M Morris Mano: Digital Logic and Computer Design, 10th Edition, Pearson, 2008.
2. A.K Maini, Varsha Agarwal, Electronic Devices and Circuit, 1st Edition, Wiley 2011
3. Ramakant A Gayakwad, "Op-Amps and Linear Integrated Circuits," Pearson, 4th Ed, 2015.

MICROPROCESSOR AND EMBEDDED SYSTEMS

Subject Code	19SEC34	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Differentiate between microprocessors and microcontrollers.
- To be familiar with the architecture and the instruction set of an Intel microprocessor Assembly language programming will be studied as well as the design of various types of digital and analog interfaces
- Identify the applicability of the embedded system.
- Comprehend the real time operating system used for the embedded system.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Design and implement programs on 8086, ARM.

CO2: Design I/O circuits.

CO3: Describe the architecture and instruction set of ARM microcontroller.

CO4: To design Embedded systems.

CO5: Design and develop modules using RTOS, Implement RPC, threads and tasks

MODULE 1

A Historical Background, The Microprocessor-Based Personal Computer Systems. The Microprocessor and its Architecture: Internal Microprocessor Architecture, Real Mode Memory Addressing.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Introduction to Protected Mode Memory Addressing, Memory Paging, Flat Mode Memory Addressing Modes: Data Addressing Modes, Program Memory Addressing Modes, Stack Memory Addressing Modes

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Data Movement Instructions: MOV Revisited, PUSH/POP, Load-Effective Address, String Data Transfers, Miscellaneous Data Transfer Instructions, Segment Override Prefix, Assembler Details. Arithmetic and Logic Instructions: Addition, Subtraction and Comparison, Multiplication and Division.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Introduction, Complex Systems and Microprocessors, Embedded Systems Design Process, formalism for system design, Design Example: Model Train Controller.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Basics of OS, Kernel, types of OSs, tasks, processes, Threads, Multitasking and Multiprocessing, Context switching, Scheduling Policies, Task Communication, Task Synchronization, Inter process Communication mechanisms.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

INTERNAL MARKS DISTRIBUTION:

3 Internals Assessment (IA) Tests are conducted for 20 marks each and it will be reduced to 40 marks. Continuous Internal Evaluation (CIE): 5 marks. (Seminars, Quiz, Surprise Test, Assignments). Attendance: 5 marks.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 1 Marks x 10 = 10Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from eachModule. 08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Barry B Brey: The Intel Microprocessors, 8th Edition, Pearson Education, 2009.
2. Wayne Wolf: Computers as Components, Principles of Embedded Computing Systems Design, 2nd Edition, Elsevier, 2008.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. The Insider's Guide to the ARM7 Based Microcontrollers, Hitex Ltd.,1st edition, 2005
2. Steve Furber, ARM System-on-Chip Architecture, Second Edition, Pearson, 2015
3. Raj Kamal, Embedded System, Tata McGraw-Hill Publishers, 2nd Edition, 2008
4. Raganandan, An Introduction to ARM System Design, Cengage Publication

ANALOG & DIGITAL ELECTRONICS LAB

Subject Code:	19SECL35	IA Marks:	50
Hours/Week:	1T+2L	Exam Hours:	3
Credits:	2	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours:	36

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This laboratory course enables students to get practical experience in design, assembly, testing and evaluation of

- BJT characteristics and Amplifiers.
- JFET Characteristics and Amplifiers.
- Power Amplifiers.
- RC-Phase shift, Hartley, Colpitts and Crystal Oscillators.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

At the end of the course students will be able to design

- CO1.** Diode Clipping and Clamping circuits
- CO2.** Voltage Regulator using Zener diode and power transistor.
- CO3.** Various amplifiers using BJT/FET
- CO4.** Oscillator Circuits
- CO5.** Circuits for studying characteristics of Operational Amplifier

Laboratory Experiments:

PART - A

1. Diode Clipping and Clamping circuits
2. Voltage Regulator using Zener diode and power transistor.
3. BJT common emitter amplifier using voltage divider bias.
4. BJT Darlington emitter follower with and without bootstrapping
5. RC-Phase shift oscillator
6. OPAMP Characteristics.

PART - B

7. Verify (a) Demorgan's Theorem for 2 variables. (b) The sum-of-product and product-of-sum expressions using universal gates.
8. Design and implement (a) Full Adder using basic logic gates. (b) Full subtractor using basic logic gates.
9. Design and implement 4-bit Parallel Adder/ subtractor using IC 7483.
10. Design and Implementation of 4-bit Magnitude Comparator using IC 7485.
11. Realize (a) 4:1 Multiplexer using gates. (b) 3-variable function using IC 74151(8:1MUX). (c) Realize 1:8 Demux and 3:8 Decoder using IC74138.
12. Synchronous UP/DOWN Counter.

Conduct of Practical Examination:

All laboratory experiments are to be included for practical examination. Question may have sub questions. Students are allowed to pick one experiment from the lot.

Write up: 15 Marks Conduction: 25 Marks Viva :10 Marks Total: 50 Marks

DIGITAL SYSTEM DESIGN LAB

Sub Code:	19SECL36	IA Marks:	50
Hrs/ Week:	1T+2L	Exam Hours:	3
Credits:	2	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours:	36

Course objectives:

To get practical experience in design, realization and verification of

- Demorgan's Theorem, SOP, POS forms
- Full/Parallel Adders, Subtractors and Magnitude Comparator
- Multiplexer using logic gates
- Demultiplexers and Decoders
- Flip-Flops, Shift registers and Counters

Course outcomes:

At the end of the course students will be able to

CO1: Define and demonstrate Demorgan's Theorem, SOP, POS forms

CO2: Design circuits using Full/Parallel Adders, Subtractors and Magnitude Comparator

CO3: Design circuits using Multiplexer using logic gates

CO4: Design circuits using Demultiplexers and Decoders

CO5: Design circuits using Flip-Flops, Shift registers and Counters

Laboratory Experiments:

1. Verify
 - (a) Demorgan's Theorem for 2 variables.
 - (b) The sum-of-product and product-of-sum expressions using universal gates.
2. Design and implement
 - (a) Full Adder using basic logic gates.
 - (b) Full subtractor using basic logic gates.
3. Design and implement 4-bit Parallel Adder/ subtractor using IC 7483.
4. Design and Implementation of 4-bit Magnitude Comparator using IC 7485.
5. Realize
 - (a) 4:1 Multiplexer using gates.
 - (b) 3-variable function using IC 74151(8:1 MUX).
6. Realize 1:8 Demux and 3:8 Decoder using IC74138.
7. Realize the following flip-flops using NAND Gates.
8. Realize the Ring Counter and Johnson Counter using IC7476
9. Asynchronous Counter.

10. Mod-8 Synchronous UP/DOWN Counter.

Conduction of Practical Examination:

1. All laboratory experiments (TEN no's) are to be included for practical examination.
2. Students are allowed to pick one experiment from the lot.
3. Strictly follow the instructions as printed on the cover page of answer script
4. Marks distribution: Procedure + Conduction + Viva:12 + 28 +10 (50)

Change of experiment is allowed only once and marks allotted to the procedure part to be made zero.

MICROPROCESSORS LABORATORY

Subject Code:	19SECL37	IA Marks:	50
Hours/Week:	1T+2L	Exam Hours:	3
Credits:	2	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours:	36

Course Objectives:

This laboratory course enables students to

- Provide practical exposure to the students on microprocessors, design and coding knowledge on 80x86 family/ARM.
- To give the knowledge and practical exposure on connectivity and execute of interfacing devices with 8086/ARM kit like LED displays, Keyboards, DAC/ADC, and various other devices

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to

- CO1.** Develop and test Assembly Language Program (ALP) using 8086/ ARM CortexM3
- CO2.** Conduct the following experiments on an ARM CortexM3 evaluation board using evaluation version of Embedded 'C' &Keil Uvision-4 tool/compiler.

Laboratory Experiments:

PART - A

Conduct the following experiments by writing Assembly Language Program (ALP) using 8086/ARM CortexM3 using an evaluation board/simulator and the required software tool.

1. Write an ALP to multiply two 16-bit binary numbers.
2. Write an ALP to find the sum of first 10 integer numbers.
3. Write an ALP to find factorial of a number.
4. Write an ALP to add an array of 16-bit numbers and store the 32-bit result in internal RAM
5. Write an ALP to find the square of a number (1 to 10) using look-up table.
6. Write an ALP to find the largest/smallest number in an array of 32 numbers.
7. Write an ALP to arrange a series of 32-bit numbers in ascending/descending order.
8. Write an ALP to count the number of ones and zeros in two consecutive memory locations.

PART- B

Conduct the following experiments on an ARM CORTEX M3 evaluation board using evaluation version of Embedded 'C' &Keil uVision-4 tool/compiler.

1. Display "Hello World" message using Internal UART.
2. Interface and Control a DC Motor.
3. Interface a Stepper motor and rotate it in clockwise and anti-clockwise direction.
4. Interface a DAC and generate Triangular and Square waveforms.
5. Interface a 4x4 keyboard and display the key code on an LCD.
6. Using the Internal PWM Module of ARM controller generate PWM and vary its duty cycle.
7. Demonstrate the use of an external interrupt to toggle an LED On/Off.

8. Display the Hex digits 0 to F on a 7-segment LED interface, with an appropriate delay in between.
9. Interface a simple Switch and display its status through Relay, Buzzer and LED.
10. Measure Ambient temperature using a sensor and SPI ADC IC.

Conduct of Practical Examination:

All laboratory experiments are to be included for practical examination. Question may have sub questions. Students are allowed to pick one experiment from the lot.

Write up: 15 Marks Conduction: 25 Marks Viva :10 Marks Total: 50 Marks

ESEP-CIRCUIT ANALYSIS, SIMULATION AND DEBUGGING

Subject Code:	19SEC38	IA Marks:	25
Hours/Week:	1T+2L	Exam Hours:	3
Credits:	2	Exam Marks:	25
		Total Hours:	36

Course Objectives:

This course enables students to

- Have acquaintance with various Open-Source Spice Simulation Tools.
- Understand how to design circuits and rig up circuits
- Use standard values of various components in designs.
- Learn Techniques to Debug the hardware and troubleshoot the problems in the circuit.

Course Outcomes:

After completion of this Course, the students will be able to

- CO1.** Analyze Electric Circuits by applying Circuit Theorems
- CO2.** Design and Analyze Electronic Circuit for simple basic applications,
- CO3.** Simulate the circuit.

PART - A

Theory, Solving Problems and Simulation of Circuit Analysis Methods and Network Theorems

Circuit Analysis

Terminology: Node, Loop, Path & Branch, Practical sources, Source transformations, Kirchhoff's Laws, Voltage and Current division rules.

Network reduction using Star – Delta transformation, Loop and node analysis with linearly dependent and independent sources for DC and AC networks.

Concepts of super node and super mesh.

Network Theorems:

Super Position Principle - Thevenin's& Norton's Theorem - Reciprocity Theorem - Compensation Theorem - Millman's Theorem - Maximum Power Transfer Theorem
Application of Network theorem: Resistance Measurement

PART - B

Simulation of Circuits Using Open-Source Tools

1. Transistor /FET Biasing Circuits.
2. Amplifiers, Feedback and Power amplifiers
3. Logic Circuits: Flip flops, Counter ICs

Examination Conduction:

Problems/Questions from Theory and all experiments are to be included for examination.

Students are allowed to pick one experiment from the lot.

Design the given circuit /Solve the circuit problem (10 Marks)

Simulation of the circuit to validate the result. (15 Marks)

PART-A: EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME - 1

Subject Code:	19SQA39	IA Marks:	50
Hours/Week:	2	Total Hours:	25
Credits:	2		

Course Objectives:

This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations with Domain specific training in respective branches.

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Learn domain specific knowledge
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART - A

Number system - "a. Number system b. Power cycle c. Remainder cycle d. Factors, Multiples e. HCF and LCM f. Trailing Zeroes", **Data arrangements and Blood relations** - "a. Linear Arrangement b. Circular Arrangement c. Multi-dimensional Arrangement d. Blood Relation e. Option elimination method in Blood Relation"

Time and work - "a. Work with different efficiencies b. Alternate Day work c. Pipes and cisterns d. Work equivalence e. Division of wages f. Leaving the work concept with example "**Coding & decoding, Number Series, Analogy, Odd man out** - "a. Different types of Problems on Coding and Decoding b. Mixed Series, alternate Series, mixed operational series c. Analogy d. Odd Man Out

Reading comprehension - "a. Types and Tackling Strategies b. Understanding meaning of a text. c. Drawing Connections. d. Summarizing and Synthesizing. e. Building Vocabulary f. Speed Reading Strategies." **Antonyms & Synonyms** - "a. Understanding root words. b. Prefixes. c. Suffixes. d. Vocabulary building. e. Putting words into context. f. Word Power made easy. g. Elimination.

PART - B

Analog Electronics

Network analysis and synthesis

Microprocessor

Digital Electronics

Assessment pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple choice questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books

1. Quantitative abilities by Arun Sharma
2. Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
3. Verbal and Non-Verbal reasoning by R S Agrawal

PART-B: INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS – 1

Subject Code	19SQA39	IA Marks	-
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Have exposure on the latest development

CO2: Acquire new skills

CO3: Become Industry ready

CO4: Have more confidence

CO5: Get additional knowledge

About the Course:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

Note:

- Student has to undergo this course wherever prescribed in the scheme. The certification course must be completed in-campus in offline mode only.
- If a student is unable to produce certificate even after two attempts, such students will be awarded 2 credits with lower grade of passing.

ADDITIONAL MATHEMATICS - I
(MANDATORY LEARNING COURSE: COMMON TO ALL BRANCHES)
(A BRIDGE COURSE FOR LATERAL ENTRY STUDENTS OF III SEM. B. TECH.)

Subject Code	19SMADIP301	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/ Week	02 (L)+00 (T)	Exam Marks	50
Total number of Lecture Hours	25	Total Marks	100
Credits		Exam Hours	02

Course Objectives:

- Basic concepts of Complex Trigonometry
- Vector Algebra
- Differential & Integral Calculus
- Vector Differentiation

Course Outcomes: On completion of the course, students are able to:

- CO1: Understand the fundamental concepts of complex numbers and vector algebra to analyze the problems arising in related area.
- CO2: Use derivatives and partial derivatives to calculate rates of change of multivariate functions.
- CO3: Learn techniques of integration including double and triple integrals to find area, volume mass and moment of inertia of plane and solid region.
- CO4: Analyze position, velocity and acceleration in two or three dimensions using the calculus of vector valued functions.
- CO5: Recognize and solve first-order ordinary differential equations occurring in different branches of engineering.

Module 1

Complex Trigonometry: Complex Numbers: Definitions & properties. Modulus and amplitude of a complex number, Argand's diagram, De-Moivre's theorem (without proof). Vector Algebra: Scalar and vectors. Vectors addition and subtraction. Multiplication of vectors (Dot and Cross products). Scalar and vector triple products simple problems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept **5 Hours**

Module 2

Differential Calculus: Review of successive differentiation. Formulae for nth derivatives of standard functions- Polar curves –angle between the radius vector and the tangent - Problems. Maclaurin's series expansions- Illustrative examples.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept **5 Hours**

Module 3

Partial Differentiation : Euler's theorem for homogeneous functions of two variables. Total derivatives differentiation of composite function. Application to Jacobians.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

5 Hours

Module 4

Integral Calculus: Statement of reduction formulae for $\sin^n x$, $\cos^n x$ and $\sin^n x \cos^n x$ and evaluation of these with standard limits-Examples. Double integrals-Simple examples.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

5 Hours

Module 5

Vector Differentiation: Differentiation of vector functions. Velocity and acceleration of a particle moving on a space curve. Scalar and vector point functions. Gradient, Divergence, Curl and Laplacian (Definitions only). Solenoidal and irrotational vector fields problems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

5 Hours

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 1 Marks x 10 = 10 Marks
PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each Module. 08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. B.S. Grewal: Higher Engineering Mathematics, Khanna publishers, 43rd edition

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. E. Kreyszig: Advanced Engineering Mathematics, John Wiley & Sons, 10th Ed., 2015.
2. N.P.Bali and Manish Goyal: Engineering Mathematics, Laxmi Publishers, 7th Ed., 2007

PROBABILITY THEORY AND STATISTICAL METHODS			
Subject Code	19SMA41	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/ Week	04 (L)+01 (T)	Exam Marks	50
Total number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

Course Objectives:

The purpose of this course is to make students well conversant with the following

- Numerical methods to solve ordinary differential equations
- complex analysis techniques applied to diverse situation in engineering
- sampling theory will reflect the range of variation in the population
- Laplace transforms
- numerical methods for ordinary differential equations

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Understand the analyticity, potential fields, residues and poles of complex potentials in field theory and electromagnetic theory.

CO2: Solve problems on probability distributions relating to digital signal processing, information theory and optimization concepts of stability of design and structural engineering.

CO3: Determine joint probability distributions with the multivariable

CO4: Draw the validity of the hypothesis proposed for the given sampling distribution in accepting or rejecting the hypothesis.

Module 1

Analytic function: Review of a function of a complex variable, limits, continuity and differentiability. Analytic functions-Cauchy-Riemann equations in Cartesian and polar forms (no proof). Properties and construction of analytic functions by Milne Thomson method

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 2

Probability: Introduction. Sample space and events. Axioms of probability. Addition and multiplication theorems. Conditional probability – illustrative examples.

Probability Distributions: Random variables (discrete and continuous), probability mass/density functions. Binomial distribution, Poisson distribution. Exponential and normal distributions, problems

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 3

Complex integration. Line integral of a complex function-Cauchy's theorem and Cauchy's integral formula and problem. Residue theorem. Bilinear transformations- problem.

Joint probability distribution: Joint Probability distribution for two discrete random variables, expectation, covariance, correlation coefficient

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 4

Statistical Methods: Review of measures of central tendency and dispersion. Correlation-Karl Pearson’s coefficient of correlation-problems. Regression analysis- lines of regression (without proof) –problems

Curve Fitting: Curve fitting by the method of least squares- fitting of the curves of the form, $y = ax + b$, $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ and $y = ae^{bx}$

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 5

Sampling Theory: Sampling, Sampling distributions, standard error, test of hypothesis for means and proportions, confidence limits for means, student’s t-distribution, Chi-square distribution as a test of goodness of fit.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini-Project/ solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 1 Marks x 10 = 10 Marks
 PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each Module. 08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. E. Kreyszig: Advanced Engineering Mathematics, John Wiley& Sons, 10th Ed. (Reprint), 2017.
2. B.S. Grewal: Higher Engineering Mathematics, Khanna Publishers, 44th Ed., 2017.

3. Srimanta Pal & Subobh C Bhunia: “Engineering Mathematics”, Oxford University Press, 3rd Reprint, 2016.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. C. Ray Wylie, Louis C. Barrett: “Advanced Engineering Mathematics”, 6th Edition, 2. McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1995.
2. S. S. Sastry: “Introductory Methods of Numerical Analysis”, 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010
3. B. V. Ramana: "Higher Engineering Mathematics" 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010.
4. N. P. Bali and Manish Goyal, “A Text Book of Engineering Mathematics”, Laxmi Publications. Latest edition, 2014.
5. Chandrika Prasad and Reena Garg “Advanced Engineering mathematics, Latest edition, Khanna Publishing, 2018.

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF ALGORITHMS			
Subject Code	19SEC42	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/ Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

Course Objectives:

This course will enable students to

- Explain various computational problem-solving techniques.
- Apply appropriate method to solve a given problem.
- Describe various methods of algorithm analysis.

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to

CO1. Describe computational solution to well-known problems like searching, sorting etc.

CO2. Estimate the computational complexity of different algorithms.

CO3. Devise an algorithm using appropriate design strategies for problem solving.

Module 1

Introduction: What is an Algorithm? (T2:1.1), Algorithm Specification (T2:1.2), Analysis Framework (T1:2.1), Performance Analysis: Space complexity, Time complexity (T2:1.3). Asymptotic Notations: Big-Oh notation (O), Omega notation (Ω), Theta notation (Θ), and Little-oh notation (o), Mathematical analysis of non-Recursive and recursive Algorithms with Examples (T1:2.2, 2.3, 2.4).

Important Problem Types: Sorting, Searching, String processing, Graph Problems, Combinatorial Problems. Fundamental Data Structures: Stacks, Queues, Graphs, Trees, Sets and Dictionaries. (T1:1.3, 1.4).

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 2

Divide and Conquer: General method, Binary search, Recurrence equation for divide and conquer, Finding the maximum and minimum (T2:3.1, 3.3, 3.4), Merge sort, Quick sort (T1:4.1, 4.2), Strassen's matrix multiplication (T2:3.8), Advantages and Disadvantages of divide and conquer. Decrease and Conquer Approach: Topological Sort. (T1:5.3)

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 3

Greedy Method: General method, Coin Change Problem, Knapsack Problem, Job sequencing with deadlines (T2:4.1, 4.3, 4.5). Minimum cost spanning trees: Prim's Algorithm, Kruskal's Algorithm (T1:9.1, 9.2). Single source shortest paths: Dijkstra's Algorithm (T1:9.3).

Optimal Tree problem: Huffman Trees and Codes (T1:9.4). Transform and Conquer Approach: Heaps and Heap Sort (T1:6.4).

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours**Module 4**

Dynamic Programming: General method with Examples, Multistage Graphs (T2:5.1, 5.2). Transitive Closure: Warshall's Algorithm, All Pairs Shortest Paths: Floyd's Algorithm, Optimal Binary Search Trees, Knapsack problem ((T1:8.2, 8.3, 8.4), Bellman-Ford Algorithm (T2:5.4), Travelling Sales Person problem (T2:5.9), Reliability design (T2:5.8).

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours**Module 5**

Backtracking: General method (T2:7.1), N-Queens problem (T1:12.1), Sum of subsets problem (T1:12.1), Graph coloring (T2:7.4), Hamiltonian cycles (T2:7.5). Branch and Bound: Assignment Problem, Travelling Sales Person problem (T1:12.2), 0/1 Knapsack problem (T2:8.2, T1:12.2): LC Branch and Bound solution (T2:8.2), FIFO Branch and Bound solution (T2:8.2). NP-Complete and NP-Hard problems: Basic concepts, nondeterministic algorithms, P, NP, NP Complete, and NP-Hard classes (T2:11.1).

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours**Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method**

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini-Project/ solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 1 Marks x 10 = 10 Marks
 PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each Module. 08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Introduction to the Design and Analysis of Algorithms, Anany Levitin., 2nd Edition, 2009. Pearson.
2. Computer Algorithms/C++, Ellis Horowitz, SatrajSahni and Rajasekaran, 2nd Edition, 2014, Universities Press

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Introduction to Algorithms, Thomas H. Cormen, Charles E. Leiserson, Ronal L. Rivest, Clifford Stein, 3rd Edition, PHI.
2. Design and Analysis of Algorithms, S. Sridhar, Oxford (Higher Education)

EM WAVES AND TRANSMISION			
Subject Code	19SEC43	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/ Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- To develop understanding about Electromagnetic and Magnetic Fields
- To introduce the concepts of Microwave Transmission Lines
- To understand Microwave Passive Devices and tubes
- To introduce the concept of Antenna Basics

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Various Laws and concepts of Electromagnetic
 CO2: Electric and Magnetic Fields and Wave Propagation
 CO3: Microwave Transmission concepts
 CO4: Microwave Passive Devices and tubes
 CO5: Antenna theory and Concepts

Module 1

Coulomb's Law, Electric Field Intensity and Flux density, Potential Experimental law of Coulomb, Electric field intensity, Field of a line charge, Electric flux density, Gauss law, Divergence, Vector Operator and divergence theorem, Definition of potential difference and potential, the potential field of point charge.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 2

Microwave Transmission Lines: Microwave Frequencies, Microwave devices, Microwave Systems, Transmission Line equations and solutions, Reflection Coefficient and Transmission Coefficient, Standing Wave and Standing Wave Ratio.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 3

Classes, Inheritance, Exceptions, Packages and Interfaces: Classes: Classes fundamentals; Declaring objects; Constructors, this keyword, garbage collection. Inheritance: inheritance basics, using super, creating multi-level hierarchy, method overriding. Exception handling: Exception handling in Java. Packages, Access Protection, Importing Packages, Interfaces.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 4

Microwave Passive Devices and tubes: Coaxial Connectors and Adapters, Attenuators, Phase Shifters, Waveguide Tees, Magic tees, Microwave Tubes, Reflex Klystron Oscillator, Mechanism of Oscillations, Modes of Oscillations.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 5

Antenna Basics: Introduction, Basic Antenna Parameters, Patterns, Beam Area, Radiation Intensity, Beam Efficiency, Directivity and Gain, Antenna Apertures, Effective Height, Bandwidth, Radio Communication Link, Antenna Field Zones

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini-Project/ solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 1 Marks x 10 = 10 Marks
PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each Module. 08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. W.H. Hayt and J.A. Buck, "Engineering Electromagnetics", 7th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2009, ISBN-978-0-07-061223-5.
2. Microwave Engineering – Annapurna Das, Sisir K Das TMH Publication, 2nd, 2010.
3. Microwave Devices and circuits- Liao, Pearson Education.
4. Antennas and Wave Propagation, John D. Krauss, Ronald J Marhefka and Ahmad S Khan, 4th Special Indian Edition, McGraw- Hill Education Pvt. Ltd., 2010.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Microwave Engineering – David M Pozar, John Wiley India Pvt. Ltd. 3rd Edn, 2008.
2. Microwave Engineering – Sushrut Das, Oxford Higher Education, 2nd Edn, 2015.
3. Antennas and Wave Propagation – Harish and Sachidananda: Oxford University Press, 2007.

PRINCIPLES OF COMMUNICATION			
Subject Code	19SEC44	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/ Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to:

- To develop understanding about performance of analog communication system.
- To introduce the concepts of various modulations and their spectral analysis.
- To understand noise impact on basic analog modulation schemes.
- To introduce the concept of analog receivers.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Understand the basics of communication system.

CO2: Apply the basic knowledge of electronic circuits and understand the effect of Noise in communication system.

CO3: Apply the basic knowledge of signals and systems and understand the concepts of various modulations and their spectral analysis.

CO4: Understand the effect of noise on AM and FM system.

CO5: Understand the operation of receivers.

Module 1

AMPLITUDE MODULATION: Introduction, Amplitude Modulation: Time & Frequency – Domain description, Switching modulator, Envelop detector.

DOUBLE SIDE BAND-SUPPRESSED CARRIER MODULATION: Time and Frequency – Domain description, Ring modulator, Coherent detection, Costas Receiver, Quadrature Carrier Multiplexing.

SINGLE SIDE-BAND AND VESTIGIAL SIDEBAND METHODS OF MODULATION: SSB Modulation, VSB Modulation, Frequency Translation, Frequency- Division Multiplexing

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 2

ANGLE MODULATION: Basic definitions, Frequency Modulation: Narrow Band FM, Wide Band FM, Transmission bandwidth of FM Signals, Generation of FM Signals, Demodulation of FM Signals, FM Stereo Multiplexing, Phase-Locked Loop: Nonlinear model of PLL, Linear model of PLL, Nonlinear Effects in FM Systems. The Super heterodyne Receiver

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 3

RANDOM VARIABLES & PROCESS: Introduction, Probability, Conditional Probability, Random variables, Several Random Variables. Statistical Averages: Function of a random variable, Moments, Random Processes, Mean, Correlation and Covariance function: Properties of autocorrelation function, Cross-correlation functions

NOISE: Shot Noise, Thermal noise, White Noise, Noise Equivalent Bandwidth

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 4

NOISE IN ANALOG MODULATION: Introduction, Receiver Model, Noise in DSB-SC receivers, Noise in AM receivers, Threshold effect, Noise in FM receivers, Capture effect, FM threshold effect, FM threshold reduction, Pre-emphasis and De-emphasis in FM

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 5

DIGITAL REPRESENTATION OF ANALOG SIGNALS: Introduction, Why Digitize Analog Sources?, The Sampling process, Pulse Amplitude Modulation, Time Division Multiplexing, Pulse-Position Modulation, Generation of PPM Waves, Detection of PPM Waves, The Quantization Process, Quantization Noise, Pulse-Code Modulation: Sampling, Quantization, Encoding, Regeneration, Decoding, Filtering, Application to Vocoder.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini-Project/ solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 1 Marks x 10 = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each Module. 08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Communication Systems, Simon Haykins & Moher, 5th Edition, John Willey, India Pvt. Ltd, 2010,

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Modern Digital and Analog Communication Systems, B. P. Lathi, Oxford University Press., 4th edition.
2. An Introduction to Analog and Digital Communication, Simon Haykins, John Wiley India Pvt. Ltd., 2008, ISBN 978–81–265–3653–5.
3. Principles of Communication Systems, H. Taub & D. L .Schilling, TMH, 2011.
4. Communication Systems, Harold P.E, Stern Samy and A. Mahmond, Pearson Edition, 2004.
5. Communication Systems: Analog and Digital, R. P. Singh and S. Sapre: TMH 2ndedition, 2007.

ANALOG COMMUNICATION LAB			
Subject Code	19SECL45	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/ Week	01 (T)+02 (L)	Exam Marks	50
Total number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	03

Course Objectives:

This course will enable students to

- Design and implement communication circuits using discrete electronic components.

Course outcomes:

1. Design filtering circuits
2. Design circuits for basic am/fm communication systems
3. Understand dac and pcm and pulse modulations
4. Simulate communication systems using matlab/scilab

Laboratory Experiments:

1. Second order active LPF, HPF, BPF and BEF.
2. AM generation and AM detection using envelope detector.
3. Balanced modulator.
4. SSB generation and demodulation using integrated circuits.
5. FM Modulator and Demodulator.
6. Pre emphasis and De emphasis
7. PAM modulation and demodulation.
8. Pulse width modulation and pulse position modulation.
9. Pulse Code Modulation and Demodulation.
10. Design and test R-2R DAC.

Student Activity:

1. Amplitude Modulation using MATLAB.
2. Frequency Modulation using MATLAB.
3. IF tuned amplifier.
4. Frequency mixer using BJT.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl no.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 mark (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	05
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per guidelines given in the regulations	05
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination.

Experiment 1: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks + Experiment 10 Marks + Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Experiment 2: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks + Experiment 10 Marks + Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Viva: 10 Marks

*Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10 Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks).

Part A: 20 Marks Part B: 20 Marks Viva :10 Marks Total: 50 Marks

ICS AND CIRCUITS LAB			
Subject Code	19SECL46	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	01 (T)+02 (L)	Exam Marks	50
Total number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	03

Course Objectives:

This laboratory course enables students to:

- Applications of various ICs : OPAMP, Timer, PLL, IC Function Generators ,Regulator ICs, UJT

Course Outcomes:

At the end of the course student will be able to

- CO1. Design basic and Application Circuits using OPAMPs
- CO2. Design and Understand ADC
- CO3. design circuits using PLL
- CO4. design circuits using Timer
- CO5. Design Relaxation oscillators

Experiments

1. Clippers and Clampers using OPAMP
2. Schmitt Trigger Design and test a Schmitt trigger circuit for the given values of UTP and LTP.
3. Sample and Hold
4. Flash ADC
5. Precision rectifiers – both Full Wave and Half Wave.
6. Design of oscillators using Op-amp.
7. Design Integrator and Differentiator using Op-Amp.
8. Design instrumentation amplifier.
9. Astable /Monostable Multivibrator using OPAMP
10. 555 Timer Astable /Monostable Multivibrator.

Student Activity:

1. Phase Locked Loops
2. Variable Regulated Power Supply
3. UJT Relaxation Oscillator

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl no.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 mark (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	05
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per guidelines given in the regulations	05
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination.

Experiment 1: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks + Experiment 10 Marks + Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Experiment 2: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks + Experiment 10 Marks + Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Viva: 10 Marks

*Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10 Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks).

Part A: 20 Marks Part B: 20 Marks Viva :10 Marks Total: 50 Marks

ALGORITHMS AND OOPS LAB			
Subject Code	19SECL47	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/ Week	01 (T)+02 (L)	Exam Marks	50
Total number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	03

Course Objectives:

This laboratory course enables students to get practical experience in

- Design of Various fundamental algorithms for problems such as sorting and searching.
- Analysis of Various fundamental algorithms
- Have a good understanding of the fundamental data structures used in computer science.

Course outcomes:

At the end of the course student will be able to

- CO1.** Understand basics of Data Structures
- CO2.** Understand basics of Algorithm design and Understand
- CO3.** Learn OOPs concepts
- CO4.** Concepts of Queues and Stack
- CO5.** Basic Concepts of Linked List

Experiments:

Part A : Programming Experiments to demonstrate Using C

1. Evaluation of expressions
2. Recursion and Backtracking
3. Sorting Algorithms
4. Searching
5. Selection Algorithms
6. String Algorithms
7. Greedy Algorithms

Part B : Basic Programs for C++ Concepts

8. Array implementation of List Abstract Data Type
9. Linked list implementation of List ADT
10. Cursor implementation of List ADT

Student activity:

1. Stack ADT - Array and linked list implementations
2. Queue ADT – Array and linked list implementations

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl no.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 mark (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	05
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per guidelines given in the regulations	05
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination.

Experiment 1: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks + Experiment 10 Marks + Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Experiment 2: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks + Experiment 10 Marks + Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Viva: 10 Marks

*Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10 Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks).

Part A: 20 Marks Part B: 20 Marks Viva :10 Marks Total: 50 Marks

ESEP- INTRODUCTION TO EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES

Subject Code:	19SEC48	IA Marks:	25
Hours/Week:	1T+2L	Exam Hours:	3
Credits:	2	Exam Marks:	25
		Total Hours:	40

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course enables students to gain knowledge on Emerging Technologies in Electronics, Communication Systems, Computers, Embedded Systems and their Applications

COURSE OUTCOMES:

After completion of this Course, the students will be able to

CO1. Analyze Electric/ Digital Circuits by applying 8051/Ardino Uno.

CO2. Design and Analyze Electronic Circuit for simple basic applications, Simulate the circuit.

Execution :Laboratory Experiments and Workshops

Theory: Brief introduction to Embedded C, Introduction to programming and write C programs to interface 8051/Ardino Uno/MSP 430 to Interfacing modules to develop single chip solutions.

Laboratory Experiments :

1. Simple Calculator using 6 digit seven segment displays and Hex Keyboard interface to 8051/Ardino Uno.
2. Alphanumeric LCD panel and Hex keypad input interface to 8051/ Ardino Uno.
3. External ADC and Temperature control interface to 8051 Ardino Uno.
4. Generate different waveforms Sine, Square, Triangular, Ramp etc. using DAC interface to 8051/ Ardino Uno. Change the frequency and amplitude.
5. Stepper motor control interface to 8051/Ardino Uno.
6. DC motor control interface to 8051/Ardino Uno.
7. Introduction to MSP430 Programming

Student activity:

1. Interfacing Temperature Sensors with 8051/Ardino Uno.
2. Activities on light and ultrasonic sensors.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / solving Challenging Problems(Student activity)	Regular mode of Assessment	05
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 1 mark (10 Lab Sessions) and lab internal	Regular mode of Assessment using Rubrics	10
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	03
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each module	02
5	Attendance	As per guidelines given in the regulations	05
Total			25

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 25 MARKS:

One program is to be performed by the students in the examination.

Program 1: 20 Marks

(Initial write up: 5 Marks + Execution of Program: 10 Marks + Result: 5 Marks)

Viva: 10 Marks

*Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of experiments with 10% reduction in Marks for one experiment.

PART-A: EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME 2

Subject Code: 19SQA49
Hours/Week: 2
Credits: 2

IA Marks: 50
Total Hours: 25

Course Objectives:

This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations. Domain specific training in respective branches with tests

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART - A

Percentages, Simple interest and Compound interest - "a. Percentages as Fractions and Decimals b. Percentage Increase / Decrease c. Simple Interest d. Compound Interest e. Relation Between Simple and Compound Interest f. Finding CI without using formula" **Data interpretation and Data sufficiency** - "a. Data Interpretation – Tables b. Data Interpretation - Pie Chart c. Data Interpretation - Bar Graph d. Data Interpretation - Line Graph e. Data Sufficiency"

Alligation and Mixture, Ratio and Proportion, Partnerships - "a. Basic Concept of Alligation and Mixture b. concept of mixture containing more than two Ingredients c. Concept and Problem-solving technic in Ratio and Proportion d. Partnership "

Permutation, Combination and Probability

"a. Fundamental Counting Principle b. Permutation and Combination c. Computation of Permutation d. Circular Permutations e. Computation of Combination f. Probability g. Total Probability h. Finding Probability without using Combination i. Finding Probability using Pascal Triangle" **Sentence correction** - "a. Subject Verb Agreement. b. Pronoun Reference and Agreement. c. Verb Tense. d. Modifier. e. Parallelism. f. Idioms. g. Comparisons. h. Prepositions. i. Determiners."

PART - B

Electromagnetic field theory
Linear integrated circuit
Communication System

Assessment pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple choice questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books

- Quantitative abilities by Arun Sharma
- Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
- Verbal and Non-Verbal reasoning by R S Agrawal

PART-B: INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS - 2

Subject Code 19SQA49

IA Marks -

Lecture -

-

Hours/Week

SEE Marks

Total Hours -

Credits 2

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Have exposure on the latest development

CO2: Acquire new skills

CO3: Become Industry ready

CO4: Have more confidence

CO5: Get additional knowledge

ABOUT THE COURSE:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

NOTE:

- Student has to undergo this course wherever prescribed in the scheme. The certification course must be completed in-campus in offline mode only.
- If a student is unable to produce certificate even after two attempts, such students will be awarded 2 credits with lower grade of passing.

DIGITAL SIGNAL PROCESSING

Subject Code	19SEC51	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to:

- Understand the mathematical description of continuous and discrete time signals and systems.
- Analyze Linear Time Invariant (LTI) systems in time and transform domains.
- The frequency domain sampling and reconstruction of discrete time signals.
- Study the properties and the development of efficient algorithms for the computation of DFT.
- Realization of FIR and IIR filters
- Learn the procedures to design of IIR filters from the analog filters.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

- CO1.** Classify the signals as continuous/discrete, periodic/apperiodic, even/odd, energy/power and deterministic/random signals.
- CO2.** Compute the response of a Continuous and Discrete LTI system using convolution integral and convolution sum.
- CO3.** Compute DFT of real and complex discrete time signals.
- CO4.** Computation of DFT using FFT algorithms and linear filtering approach.
- CO5.** Solve problems on digital filter design

MODULE 1

Introduction and Classification of signals: Definition of signal and systems, communication and control systems as examples. Sampling of analog signals, Continuous time and discrete time signal, Classification of signals as even, odd, periodic and non-periodic, energy and power. Elementary signals/Functions: Exponential, sine, impulse, step and its properties. Operations on signals: Amplitude scaling, addition, multiplication, time scaling, time shifting and time folding.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Time domain representation of LTI System: System modeling: Input-output relation, definition of impulse response, convolution sum, convolution integral, computation of convolution integral and convolution sum. System interconnection, system properties in terms of impulse response, step response in terms of impulse response.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Discrete Fourier Transforms (DFT): Frequency domain sampling and reconstruction of discrete time signals. DFT as a linear transformation. DFT properties, use of DFT in linear filtering, overlap-save and overlap-add method.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Introduction to IIR filter design: Characteristics of commonly used analog filter, Design of Butterworth filters, analog to analog frequency transformations, Design of Chebyshev filters

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Design of IIR Filters from analog filter using Impulse invariance, Bilinear transformation, Backward difference method and matched z transform method.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Simon Haykins and Barry Van Veen, —Signals and Systems, 2nd Edition, 2008, WileyIndia. ISBN 9971-51-239-4.
2. Digital signal processing – Principles Algorithms & Applications, Proakis & Monalakis, Pearson education, 4th Edition, New Delhi, 2007.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Alan V Oppenheim, Alan S, Willsky and A Hamid Nawab, —Signals and Systems, Pearson Education Asia / PHI, 2nd edition, 1997. Indian Reprint 2002.
2. Ganesh Rao and Satish Tunga, —Signals and Systems, Pearson/Sanguine Technical Publishers, 2004
3. Discrete Time Signal Processing, Oppenheim & Schaffer, PHI, 2003.
4. Digital Signal Processing, S. K. Mitra, Tata Mc-Graw Hill, 3rd Edition, 2010.

COMPUTER NETWORKS

Subject Code	19SEC52	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Demonstration of application layer protocols.
- Discuss transport layer services and understand UDP and TCP protocols.
- Explain routers, IP and Routing Algorithms in network layer.
- Disseminate the Wireless and Mobile Networks covering IEEE 802.11 Standard.
- Illustrate concepts of Multimedia Networking, Security and Network Management

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Illustrate basic computer network technology.

CO2: Identify the different types of network topologies and protocols.

CO3: Enumerate the layers of the OSI model and TCP/IP functions of each layer.

CO4: Make out the different types of network devices and their functions within a network.

CO5: Understand the concepts of Multimedia Networking, Security and Network Management.

MODULE 1

Introduction: Data Communications, Networks, Network Types, Internet History, Standards and Administration, Networks Models: Protocol Layering, TCP/IP Protocol suite, The OSI model, Introduction to Physical Layer-1: Data and Signals, Digital Signals, Transmission Impairment, Data Rate limits, Performance, Digital Transmission: Digital to digital conversion (Only Line coding: Polar, Bipolar and Manchester coding)

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Physical Layer-2: Analog to digital conversion (only PCM), Transmission Modes, Analog Transmission: Digital to analog conversion, Bandwidth Utilization: Multiplexing and Spread Spectrum, switching: Introduction, Circuit Switched Networks and Packet switching.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Error Detection and Correction: Introduction, Block coding, Cyclic codes, Checksum, Forward error correction, Data link control: DLC services, Data link layer protocols, HDLC, and Point to Point protocol (Framing, Transition phases only).

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Media Access control: Random Access, Controlled Access and Channelization, Wired LANs Ethernet: Ethernet Protocol, Standard Ethernet, Fast Ethernet, Gigabit Ethernet and 10 Gigabit Ethernet, Wireless LANs: Introduction, IEEE 802.11 Project and Bluetooth.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Other wireless Networks: WIMAX, Cellular Telephony, Satellite networks, Network layer Protocols: Internet Protocol, ICMPv4, Mobile IP, Next generation IP: IPv6 addressing, The IPv6 Protocol, The ICMPv6 Protocol and Transition from IPv4 to IPv6.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Behrouz A. Forouzan, Data Communications and Networking 5E, 5th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2013.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Alberto Leon-Garcia and Indra Widjaja: Communication Networks - Fundamental Concepts and Key architectures, 2nd Edition Tata McGraw-Hill, 2004.
2. William Stallings: Data and Computer Communication, 8th Edition, Pearson Education, 2007.

INSTRUMENTATION AND CONTROL

Subject Code	19SEC531	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Impart with the knowledge of generalized measurement systems.
- Learn the characteristics of various types of measurement systems and errors in measuring instruments.
- Understand the concepts of Ammeters, Voltmeter and Multimeters
- Impart with the basic concepts of CRO and its usage for the measurement of various parameters.
- Understand basics of Control systems

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Analyze instrument characteristics, errors and generalized measurement system.

CO2: Use of Ammeters, Voltmeter and Multimeters and CRO for measurement

CO3: Analyze and interpret different signal generator circuits for the generation of various waveforms

CO4: Understand and use different display devices and recorders

CO5: Develop transfer function for a given control system using block diagram reduction techniques and signal flow graph method.

MODULE 1

Measurement and Error: Definitions, Accuracy, Precision, Resolution and Significant Figures, Types of Errors, Measurement error combinations. Ammeters: DC Ammeter, Multirange Ammeter, The Ayrton Shunt or Universal Shunt, Extending of Ammeter Ranges. Voltmeters and Multimeters: Introduction, Basic Meter as a DC Voltmeter, DC Voltmeter, Multirange Voltmeter, Extending Voltmeter Ranges, Multimeter.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Digital Voltmeters: Introduction, RAMP technique, Dual Slope Integrating Type DVM, Integrating Type DVM, Most Commonly used principles of ADC, Successive Approximations, -Digit, Resolution and Sensitivity of Digital Meters, General Specifications of DVM, Digital Instruments: Introduction, Digital Multimeters, Digital Frequency Meter, Digital Measurement of Time, Universal Counter.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Cathode ray oscilloscope: Basic concept, Features, Storage oscilloscope. Introduction to Control Systems: Types of Control Systems, Effect of Feedback System s, Differential equation of Physical

Systems –Mechanical Systems, Electrical Systems, Electromechanical systems, Analogous Systems. Representation of Mechanical Systems, Electrical Systems, Electromechanical systems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Block diagrams and Signal flow graphs: Block diagram of control system: Representation of system, Transfer functions, Block diagram algebra and estimation of system function using signal Flow graphs.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Stability criterion of control systems: Routh stability criterion, Necessary conditions for stability, Routh array, Difficulties in the formulation of Routh Table, Application of Routh criterion.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini-Project/Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual)	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. “Electronic Instrumentation”, H. S. Kalsi, TMH, 2004
2. “Electronic Instrumentation and Measurements”, David A Bell, PHI / Pearson Education 2006/ Oxford Higher Education, 2013.
3. Electrical and Electronic Measurements and Instrumentation – A. K. Sawhney, 17th Edition (Reprint 2004), Dhanpat Rai & Co. Pvt. Ltd., 2004
4. J. Nagarath and M.Gopal, “Control Systems Engineering”, New Age International (P) Limited, Publishers, Fifth edition- 2005, ISBN: 81 - 224 - 2008-7.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. "Principles of Measurement Systems", John P. Beatly, 3rd Edition, Pearson Education, 2000
2. "Modern Electronic Instrumentation and Measuring Techniques", Cooper D & A D Helfrick, PHI, 1998.
3. "Modern Control Engineering," K.Ogata, Pearson Education Asia/ PHI, 4th Edition, 2002. ISBN 978 - 81 - 203 - 4010 - 7.
4. "Automatic Control Systems", Benjamin C. Kuo, John Wiley India Pvt. Ltd., 8th Edition, 2008.
5. "Feedback and Control System," Joseph J Distefano III et al., Schaum's Outlines, TMH, 2nd Ed

DIGITAL CONTROL

Subject Code	19SAL532	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to:

CO1: Learn Control System Terminology, Signals and processing of signals in digital control

CO2: Learn about System modeling and sample and hold systems

CO3: Study Models of Digital Control Devices and Systems

CO4: Study Algorithms for Design of Digital Control

CO5: Study Analysis of Control System using State Variable Methods

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Define Control System Terminology, Signals and describe basic processing of signals in digital control

CO2: Describe System modeling and sample and hold systems

CO3: Describe Models of Digital Control Devices and Systems

CO4: Design of Digital Control systems using basic algorithms.

CO5: Analyze Control System using State Variable Methods

MODULE 1

Control System Terminology, Computer-Based Control: History and Trends, Control Theory: History and Trends, An Overview of the Classical Approach to Analog Controller Design. Signal Processing in Digital Control: Configuration of the Basic Digital Control Scheme, Principles of Signal Conversion, Discrete-Time Signals, Time-Domain Models for Discrete-Time Systems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

The z-Transform, Transfer Function Models, Frequency Response, Stability on the z-Plane and the Jury Stability Criterion. Sample-and-Hold Systems: The Sampling operation, The Hold operation, Practical Sample-and-Hold Circuit, Sampled Spectra and Aliasing, Reconstruction of Analog Signals, Practical Aspects of the Choice of Sampling Rate, Principles of Discretization

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Models of Digital Control Devices and Systems: z-Domain Description of Sampled Continuous-Time Plants, z-Domain Description of Systems with Dead-Time, Implementation of Digital Controllers, Tunable PID Controllers, Digital Temperature Control System, Digital Position Control System, Stepping Motors and Their Control, Programmable Logic Controllers.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Design of Digital Control Algorithms: z-Plane Specifications of Control System Design, Digital Compensator Design using Frequency Response Plots, Digital Compensator Design using Root Locus Plots, z-Plane Synthesis

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Control System Analysis using State Variable Methods: Introduction to State Variable Model, relation between transfer function and state space model for a discrete time system and various standard or canonical state variable models, Characteristic Equation, Eigenvalues and Eigen vectors, Controllability and Observability, Stability of discrete state space models, Multivariable Systems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Discrete-Time Control systems – K. Ogata, Pearson Education/PHI, 2nd Edition.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Digital Control Systems, Kuo, Oxford University Press, 2nd Edition, 2003.
2. Digital Control and State Variable Methods by M.Gopal, TMH

AUTOMOTIVE ELECTRONICS

Subject Code	19SAL533	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basics of automobile dynamics
- Design electronics to complement those features.
- Design and implement the electronics that attribute the reliability, safety
- Design and implement the electronics that provide smartness to the automobiles
- Design and implement the electronics providing add-on comforts.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Acquire an overview of automotive components, subsystems, and basics of Electronic Engine Control in today's automotive industry.

CO2: Use available automotive sensors and actuators while interfacing with microcontrollers / microprocessors during automotive system design.

CO3: Understand the networking of various modules in automotive systems, communication protocols and diagnostics of the sub systems.

CO4: Design and implement the electronics that attribute the reliability, safety.

CO5: Design electronics that provides smartness to the automobiles, providing add-on comforts.

MODULE 1

Automotive Fundamentals Overview – Evolution of Automotive Electronics, Automobile Physical Configuration, Survey of Major Automotive Systems, The Engine – Engine Block, Cylinder Head, Four Stroke Cycle, Engine Control, Ignition System - Spark plug, High voltage circuit and distribution, Spark pulse generation, Ignition Timing, Diesel Engine, Drive Train - Transmission, Drive Shaft, Differential, Suspension, Brakes, Steering System (Text 1: Chapter1), Starter Battery – Operating principle. The Basics of Electronic Engine Control – Motivation for Electronic Engine Control – Exhaust Emissions, Fuel Economy, Concept of an Electronic Engine control system, Definition of General terms, Definition of Engine performance terms, Engine mapping, Effect of Air/Fuel ratio, spark timing and EGR on performance, Control Strategy, Electronic Fuel control system, Analysis of intake manifold pressure, Electronic Ignition.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Automotive Control System applications of Sensors and Actuators – Typical Electronic Engine Control System, Variables to be measured, Automotive Sensors – Airflow rate sensor, Strain Gauge MAP sensor, Engine Crankshaft Angular Position Sensor, Magnetic Reluctance Position Sensor, Hall effect Position Sensor, Shielded Field Sensor, Optical Crankshaft Position Sensor, Throttle Angle Sensor (TAS), Engine Coolant Temperature (ECT) Sensor, Exhaust Gas Oxygen (O₂/EGO) Lambda Sensors, Piezoelectric Knock Sensor. Automotive Actuators – Solenoid, Fuel Injector, EGR Actuator, Ignition System

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Digital Engine Control Systems – Digital Engine control features, Control modes for fuel Control (Seven Modes), EGR Control, Electronic Ignition Control - Closed loop Ignition timing, Spark Advance Correction Scheme, Integrated Engine Control System - Secondary Air Management, Evaporative Emissions Canister Purge, Automatic System Adjustment, System Diagnostics. Control Units – Operating conditions, Design, Data processing, Programming, Digital modules in the Control unit, Control unit software.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Automotive Networking –Bus Systems – Classification, Applications in the vehicle, Coupling of networks, Examples of networked vehicles, Buses - CAN Bus, LIN Bus, MOST Bus, Bluetooth, Flex Ray, Diagnostic Interfaces. Vehicle Motion Control – Typical Cruise Control System, Digital Cruise Control System, Digital Speed Sensor, Throttle Actuator, Digital Cruise Control configuration, Cruise Control Electronics (Digital only), Antilock Brake System (ABS).

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Automotive Diagnostics–Timing Light, Engine Analyzer, On-board diagnostics, Off-board diagnostics, Expert Systems, Occupant Protection Systems – Accelerometer based Air Bag systems. Future Automotive Electronic Systems – Alternative Fuel Engines, Electric and Hybrid vehicles, Fuel cell powered cars, Collision Avoidance Radar warning Systems, Low tire pressure warning system, Heads Up display, Speech Synthesis, Navigation – Navigation Sensors - Radio Navigation, Signpost navigation, dead reckoning navigation, Voice Recognition Cell Phone dialing, Advanced Cruise Control, Stability Augmentation, Automatic driving Control.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. William B. Ribbens, “Understanding Automotive Electronics”, 6th Edition, Elsevier Publishing.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Robert Bosch Gmbh (Ed.) Bosch Automotive Electrics and Automotive Electronics Systems and Components, Networking and Hybrid Drive, 5th edition, John Wiley& Sons Inc., 2007.

MEDICAL ELECTRONICS

Subject Code	19SAL534	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- To gain knowledge about the various physiological parameters both electrical and non-electrical and the methods of recording and also the method of transmitting these parameters
- To study about the various assist devices used in the hospitals
- To gain knowledge about equipment used for physical medicine and the various recently developed diagnostic and therapeutic techniques.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Know the human body electro- physiological parameters and recording of bio-potentials

CO2: Comprehend the non-electrical physiological parameters and their measurement – body temperature, blood pressure, pulse, blood cell count, blood flow meter etc.

CO3: Interpret the various assist devices used in the hospitals viz. pacemakers, defibrillators, dialyzers and ventilators

CO4: Comprehend physical medicine methods eg. ultrasonic, shortwave, microwave surgical diathermies, and bio-telemetry principles and methods

CO5: Know about recent trends in medical instrumentation

MODULE 1

Bioelectric signals; Cell characteristics. Bio-electric potential: Origin, Resting and action potential, depolarization and repolarization, propagation of action potentials, ECG, EEG and EMG waveforms with typical characteristics. Electrodes: Types, Electrodes used for ECG, EEG and EMG. Selection of physiological transducers.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Basic recording systems. Block diagram of ECG, isolated preamplifier, ECG leads, effects of artifacts on ECG recordings, Multichannel ECG machine, Block diagram of EEG machine, 10-20 electrode placement system for EEG, and Evoked potential. Working of EMG with block diagram. Applications of ECG, EEG, EMG and ERG recordings.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Assist Devices: Cardiac pacemakers, DC Defibrillator, Dialyser, Ventilators, Magnetic Resonance Imaging Systems, Ultrasonic Imaging Systems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Blood constituents- calculation of size of cells- MCV, MCH, MCHC, MPV, RDW& PDW, Blood cell counter- Coulter's method and Dark field method, Digital pH meter, Spectrophotometer, Oximetry – fingertip oximeter. Features of Blood flow meters. Ultrasonic Doppler-shift based FHR measurement. BP measurement-systolic & diastolic pressure, direct method and indirect methods, BP measurement using ultrasonic doppler shift method, advantages & disadvantages. Rheographic method of indirect blood flow measurement.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

X-Rays- properties, X-ray imaging machine, applications, advantages and disadvantages. Computerized tomography- basic principle, block diagram of a typical CT imaging system, advantages, disadvantages and applications of CT imaging. Magnetic resonance imaging principles of NMR imaging, basic components of a typical NMR imaging system, applications, advantages and disadvantages of magnetic resonance imaging. Ultra-sonic imaging-properties of ultrasonic waves, basic pulse echo apparatus. Concept and features of patient monitoring system.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Leslie Cromwell, Biomedical Instrumentation and Measurement, Prentice Hall of India, New Delhi, 2007.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Khandpur, R.S., Handbook of Biomedical Instrumentation, TATA Mc Graw-Hill, New Delhi, 2003.

2. John G.Webster, Medical Instrumentation Application and Design, 3rd Edition, Wiley India Edition, 2007
3. Joseph J.Carr and John M.Brown, Introduction to Biomedical Equipment Technology, John.

AVIATION ELECTRONICS

Subject Code	19SEC535	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the aircraft system design parameters and specifications
- Understand the aircraft control systems.
- Understand the aircraft Engine systems.
- Acquire the knowledge of aircraft instruments.
- Acquire the knowledge on new avionics systems

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Define the required design parameters and specifications for aircraft systems.

CO2: Distinguish the conventional and modern control systems.

CO3: Classify the aircraft systems.

CO4: Categorize different types of aircraft instruments.

CO5: Describe new avionics systems

MODULE 1

Introduction to avionics - Systems design parameters and specifications - Traceability - Ilities - Avionics architecture - LRU/LRM - Backplane standards - Data bus – topologies - word formats - MIL-STD 1553B - ARINC 429 - ARINC 629 - CSDB – FCAD.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Aircraft Systems: Hydraulic systems, Study of typical workable system, components, Pneumatic systems, Advantages, Working principles, Typical Air pressure system, Brake system, Typical Pneumatic power system, Components, Landing Gear systems, Classification.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Engine Systems: Fuel systems for Piston and jet engines, Components of multi engines. lubricating systems for piston and jet engines – Starting and Ignition systems – Typical examples for piston and jet engines.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Aircraft Instruments: Flight Instruments and Navigation Instruments, Gyroscope, Accelerometers, Air speed Indicators, TAS, EAS, Mach Meters, Altimeters, Principles and operation, Study of various

types of engine instruments, Tachometers, Temperature gauges, Pressure gauges, Operation and Principles.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

New avionics systems - Cockpit instruments - User interface - Navigation - Guidance and Flight Control - Stores management system - Data communications.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Ian Moir and Allan Seabridge, Aircraft Systems: Mechanical, Electrical and Avionics-Subsystem Integration', Wiley India Pvt Ltd, 3rd edition, 2012, ISBN-13: 978-8126535217.
2. Pallet, E.H.J., Aircraft Instruments and Integrated Systems, Longman Scientific and Technical, 1996.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Lalit Gupta and OP. Sharma, Aircraft Systems (Fundamentals of Flight Vol. IV)',
2. Treager. S, Gas Turbine Technology, McGraw-Hill, 3rd edition, 2013, ISBN-13: 9781259064876.
3. R.W. Sloley and W.H. Coulthard, The aircraft Engineers Handbook, No 4, Instruments', 6 Edition, 2005, ISBN-13: 978-8175980518
4. SR. Majumdar, Pneumatic Systems', Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Co, 1st Edition, 2001, ISBN-13: 978-0074602317.
5. William A Neese, Aircraft Hydraulic Systems', Himalayan Books, 2007.

OPERATING SYSTEMS

Subject Code	19SAL541	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Introduce concepts and terminology used in OS.
- Explain threading and multithreaded systems.
- Illustrate process synchronization and concept of Deadlock.
- Introduce Memory and Virtual memory management.
- Introduce File system and storage techniques.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

- CO1: Demonstrate need for OS and different types of OS.
- CO2: Apply suitable techniques for management of different resources.
- CO3: Use processor, memory, storage and file system commands.
- CO4: Realize the different concepts of OS in platform of usage through case studies.
- CO5: Analyze on different storage techniques.

MODULE 1

Introduction to operating systems, System structures: What operating systems do; Computer System organization; Computer System architecture; Operating System structure; Operating System operations; Process management; Memory management; Storage management; Protection and Security; Distributed system; Special-purpose systems; Computing environments. Operating System Services; User - Operating System interface; System calls; Types of system calls; System programs; Operating system design and implementation; Operating System structure; Virtual machines; Operating System generation; System boot.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Process Management Process concept; Process scheduling; Operations on processes; Inter process communication. Multi-threaded Programming: Overview; Multithreading models; Thread Libraries; Threading issues. Process Scheduling: Basic concepts; Scheduling Criteria; Scheduling Algorithms; Multiple-processor scheduling; Thread scheduling. Process Synchronization: Synchronization: The critical section problem; Peterson's solution; Synchronization hardware; Semaphores; Classical problems of synchronization; Monitors.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Deadlocks: Deadlocks; System model; Deadlock characterization; Methods for handling deadlocks; Deadlock prevention; Deadlock avoidance; Deadlock detection and recovery from deadlock. Memory Management: Memory management strategies: Background; Swapping; Contiguous memory allocation; Paging; Structure of page table; Segmentation.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Virtual Memory Management: Background; Demand paging; Copy-on-write; Page replacement; Allocation of frames; Thrashing. File System, Implementation of File System: File system: File concept; Access methods; Directory structure; File system mounting; File sharing; Protection: Implementing File system: File system structure; File system implementation; Directory implementation; Allocation methods; Free space management.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Secondary Storage Structures, Protection: Mass storage structures; Disk structure; Disk attachment; Disk scheduling; Disk management; Swap space management. Protection: Goals of protection, Principles of protection, Domain of protection, Access matrix, Implementation of access matrix, Access control, Revocation of access rights, Capability- Based systems. Case Study: The Linux Operating System: Linux history; Design principles; Kernel modules; Process management; Scheduling; Memory Management; File systems, Input and output; Inter-process communication.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Abraham Silberschatz, Peter Baer Galvin, Greg Gagne, Operating System Principles 7th edition, Wiley-India, 2006.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Ann McHoes Ida M Fylnn, Understanding Operating System, Cengage Learning, 6th Edition

2. D.M Dhamdhere, Operating Systems: A Concept Based Approach 3rd Ed, McGraw-Hill, 2013.
3. P.C.P. Bhatt, An Introduction to Operating Systems: Concepts and Practice 4th Edition, PHI(EEE), 2014.
4. William Stallings Operating Systems: Internals and Design Principles, 6th Edition, Pearson.

NANOELECTRONICS

Subject Code	19SEC542	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

CO1: Understand present CMOS VLSI device design and fundamental limits of operation

CO2: Study MOS based silicon devices and various multi gate devices

CO3: Understand SOI devices and its performance comparison with Silicon devices Curriculum and

CO4: Understand the underlying concepts by setting up and solving the Schrödinger equation for different types of potentials in one dimension as well as in 2 or 3 dimensions for specific cases.

CO5: Understand nano electronic systems and building blocks such as: low-dimensional semiconductors, hetero structures, carbon nanotubes, quantum dots, nanowires etc.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: To introduce the challenges faced by present CMOS VLSI device design and fundamental limits of operation

CO2: To study novel MOS based silicon devices and various multi gate devices

CO3: To learn about SOI devices and its performance comparison with Silicon devices

CO4: To Explain the underlying concepts by setting up and solving the Schrödinger equation for different types of potentials in one dimension as well as in 2 or 3 dimensions for specific cases.

CO5: To describe nano electronic systems and building blocks such as: low-dimensional semiconductors, heterostructures, carbon nanotubes, quantum dots, nanowires etc.

MODULE 1

Challenges going to sub-100 nm MOSFETs – Oxide layer thickness, tunneling, power density, non-uniform dopant concentration, threshold voltage scaling, lithography, hot electron effects, sub-threshold current, velocity saturation, interconnect issues, fundamental limits for MOS operation.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Novel MOS-based devices – Multiple gate MOSFETs, Silicon-on-insulator, Silicon-on nothing, FinFETs, vertical MOSFETs, strained Si devices.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Quantum structures – quantum wells, quantum wires and quantum dots, Single electron devices charge quantization, energy quantization, Coulomb blockade, Coulomb staircase.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Heterostructure based devices – Type I, II and III heterojunctions, Si-Ge heterostructure, heterostructures of III-V and II-VI compounds - resonant tunneling devices (diodes & transistors).

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Carbon nanotubes-based devices – CNFET, characteristics Spintronics - Spin-based devices – spinFET, characteristics.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Mircea Dragoman and Daniela Dragoman: Nanoelectronics – Principles & devices; Artech House Publishers, 2005.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Karl Goser: Nanoelectronics and Nanosystems: From Transistors to Molecular and Quantum Devices, Springer 2005.
2. Mark Lundstrom and Jing Guo: Nanoscale Transistors: Device Physics, Modeling and Simulation, Springer, 2005.
3. Vladimir V Mitin, Viatcheslav A Kochelap and Michael A Stroscio: Quantum heterostructures; Cambridge University Press, 1999 5. S M Sze (Ed): High speed semiconductor devices, Wiley, 1990.

MEMS & NANO TECHNOLOGY

Subject Code	19SEC543	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- learn the trends in development and synthesizing of nano systems.
- Understand measuring systems to nano scale.
- To expose the students to the evolution of Nano systems, to the various fabrication techniques.
- Study about nano materials and various nano measurements techniques.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Explain MEMS and Methods for Processing MEMS materials

CO2: Describe characteristic techniques of micro system fabrication process

CO3: Describe the evolution of Nano technology

CO4: Use nano materials and various nano measurements techniques in applications

CO5: Involve in research on nano scale manufacturing

MODULE 1

Historical background development of microelectronics, evolution of micro sensors, MEMS, emergence of micro machines. Micro sensors: Introduction, thermal sensors, mechanical sensors, flow sensors and Introduction to SAW DEVICES.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Overview, metals, semiconductors, ceramic, polymeric and composite materials, Micro stereo lithography: Introduction, Scanning Method, Projection Method, Applications. LIGA Process: Introduction, Basic Process and Application.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Photolithography, Chemical Vapor Deposition, Etching, Bulk and Surface Micro Manufacturing.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Module 4

Introduction to Nanotechnology, The nanoscale. Consequences of the nanoscale for technology and society. - Technologies for the Nanoscale, Top-down versus bottom-up assembly. Visualization, manipulation and characterization at the nanoscale, Proximal probe technologies. Self-assembly.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Nano manipulation, Nanolithography - An introduction to tribology and its industrial applications – Nanoscale Materials and Structure, Nano composites, Safety issues with nanoscale powders - Applications, Applications in energy, informatics, medicine, etc.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Mark Ratner & Daniel Ratner, Nano Technology, Pearson Education, 2003.
2. Tai – Ran Hsu, “MEMS & MICROSYSTEMS Design and Manufacturing”, TATA McGRAW-HILL, 2002
3. S.M. Sze, Semiconductor Sensors, John Wiley & Sons, INC., 1994.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Marc J. Madou, “Fundamentals of Microfabrication”, II Edition, CRC Press, 2002.
2. Mohamed Gad-el-Hak, The MEMS Handbook, CRC Press, 2002
3. M.Elwenspoek, R.Wiegerink, Mechanical Microsensors, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, 2001.
4. David Ferry, Transport in Nanostructures, Cambridge University Press, 2000.
5. S. Datta, Electron Transport in Mesoscopic Systems, Cambridge University Press, 1995.
6. Beenaker and Van Houten, Quantum Transport in Semiconductor Nanostructures, in Solid State Physics v. 44, eds. Eherreich and Turnbull, Academic Press, 1991.
7. P. Rai-Choudhury, Handbook of Microlithography, Micromachining & Microfabrication, SPIE, 1997.

MEMS & NANO TECHNOLOGY

Subject Code	19SEC543	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- learn the trends in development and synthesizing of nano systems.
- Understand measuring systems to nano scale.
- To expose the students to the evolution of Nano systems, to the various fabrication techniques.
- Study about nano materials and various nano measurements techniques.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO6: Explain MEMS and Methods for Processing MEMS materials

CO7: Describe characteristic techniques of micro system fabrication process

CO8: Describe the evolution of Nano technology

CO9: Use nano materials and various nano measurements techniques in applications

CO10: Involve in research on nano scale manufacturing

MODULE 1

Historical background development of microelectronics, evolution of micro sensors, MEMS, emergence of micro machines. Micro sensors: Introduction, thermal sensors, mechanical sensors, flow sensors and Introduction to SAW DEVICES.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Overview, metals, semiconductors, ceramic, polymeric and composite materials, Micro stereo lithography: Introduction, Scanning Method, Projection Method, Applications. LIGA Process: Introduction, Basic Process and Application.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Photolithography, Chemical Vapor Deposition, Etching, Bulk and Surface Micro Manufacturing.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Module 4

Introduction to Nanotechnology, The nanoscale. Consequences of the nanoscale for technology and society. - Technologies for the Nanoscale, Top-down versus bottom-up assembly. Visualization, manipulation and characterization at the nanoscale, Proximal probe technologies. Self-assembly.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Nano manipulation, Nanolithography - An introduction to tribology and its industrial applications – Nanoscale Materials and Structure, Nano composites, Safety issues with nanoscale powders - Applications, Applications in energy, informatics, medicine, etc.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Mark Ratner & Daniel Ratner, Nano Technology, Pearson Education, 2003.
2. Tai – Ran Hsu, “MEMS & MICROSYSTEMS Design and Manufacturing”, TATA McGRAW-HILL, 2002
3. S.M. Sze, Semiconductor Sensors, John Wiley & Sons, INC., 1994.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Marc J. Madou, “Fundamentals of Microfabrication”, II Edition, CRC Press, 2002.
2. Mohamed Gad-el-Hak, The MEMS Handbook, CRC Press, 2002
3. M.Elwenspoek, R.Wiegerink, Mechanical Microsensors, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, 2001.
4. David Ferry, Transport in Nanostructures, Cambridge University Press, 2000.
5. S. Datta, Electron Transport in Mesoscopic Systems, Cambridge University Press, 1995.
6. Beenaker and Van Houten, Quantum Transport in Semiconductor Nanostructures, in Solid State Physics v. 44, eds. Eherreich and Turnbull, Academic Press, 1991.
7. P. Rai-Choudhury, Handbook of Microlithography, Micromachining & Microfabrication, SPIE, 1997.

REAL TIME SYSTEMS

Subject Code	19SEC544	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Discuss the historical background of Real-time systems and its classifications.
- Describe the concepts of computer control and hardware components for RealTime Application.
- Discuss the languages to develop software for Real-Time Applications.
- Explain the concepts of operating system and RTS development methodologies.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Understand the fundamentals of Real time systems and its classifications.

CO2: Understand the concepts of computer control, operating system

CO3: Understand the suitable computer hardware requirements for real-time applications.

CO4: Develop the software languages to meet Real time applications.

CO5: Apply suitable methodologies to design and develop Real-Time Systems.

MODULE 1

Introduction to Real-Time Systems: Historical background, Elements of a Computer Control System, RTS- Definition, Classification of Real-time Systems, Time Constraints, Classification of Programs. Concepts of Computer Control: Introduction, Sequence Control, Loop Control, Supervisory Control, Centralized Computer Control, Hierarchical Systems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Computer Hardware Requirements for Real-Time Applications: Introduction, General Purpose Computer, Single Chip Microcomputers and Microcontrollers, Specialized Processors, Process-Related Interfaces, Data Transfer Techniques, Communications, Standard Interface.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Languages for Real-Time Applications: Introduction, Syntax Layout and Readability, Declaration and Initialization of Variables and Constants, Modularity and Variables, Compilation of Modular Programs, Data types, Control Structures, Exception Handling, Low-level facilities, Co-routines, Interrupts and Device Handling, Concurrency, Real-Time Support, Overview of Real-Time Languages.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Module 4

Operating Systems: Introduction, Real-Time Multi-Tasking OS, Scheduling Strategies, Priority Structures, Task Management, Scheduler and Real-Time Clock Interrupt Handler, Memory Management, Code Sharing, Resource Control, Task Co-Operation and Communication, Mutual Exclusion.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Design of RTS – General Introduction: Introduction, Specification Document, Preliminary Design, Single-Program Approach, Foreground/Background System. RTS Development Methodologies: Introduction, Yourdon Methodology, Ward and Mellor Method, Hatley and Pirbhai Method.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Real-Time Computer Control, by Stuart Bennet, 2nd Edn. Pearson Education. 2008.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. C.M. Krishna, Kang G. Shin, "Real-Time Systems", McGraw-Hill International Editions, 1997.
2. Real-Time Systems Design and Analysis, Phillip. A. Laplante, second edition, PHI, 2005.
3. Embedded Systems, Raj Kamal, Tata McGraw Hill, India, third edition, 2005.

CONSUMER ELECTRONICS

Subject Code	19SEC545	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Learn about Electronics Audio Systems Telecommunication Systems.
- Understand the Television Principles.
- Study the technologies applied in various home appliances.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: List technical specification of electronics Audio system.

CO2: Identify and explain working of various colour TV transmission blocks.

CO3: Describe functions of various internal blocks of home appliances.

CO4: Trouble shoots consumer electronics products like TV, washing machine and AC.

CO5: Understand the basic functions of various consumer electronic goods.

MODULE 1

Audio System: Microphones, Tape recorder, Audio compact disc system, High fidelity Audio system, Stereo sound system, Loudspeaker, Public address system, Magnetic sound recording. Telecommunication Systems: Basics of Telephone system, Caller ID Telephone, Intercoms, Cordless Telephones, Cellular mobile systems

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Television: Introduction, Radio and TV Transmission & Reception, Block diagram of TV transmitter, Television studies and Equipment, Antenna for TV transmitter, Block diagram of TV receiver, TV camera tube, Persistence of vision, Scanning, Synchronization, CCTR-B System, Composite video signal, B, NTSC, SECAM signal, compatibility, CCTV, Cable TV, HDTV.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Audio signal modulation, TV channel, Television Rx antenna, Feeder cable, Balun T/F, Monochrome picture tube, Black & white TV Rx, Colour TV signal, Colour TV Rx, PAL. Home Electronics: Digital Camera system, Microwave ovens, Washing Machines, Air Conditioners and Refrigerators.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Module 4

Miscellaneous Devices: Digital watch, Calculators, An electronic guessing game, Cordless Telephone, Mobile telephone, Cellular telephone, Battery telephone, Battery Eliminator, Battery

charger, DC supply, DC supply operational amplifier, IC regulator, UPS, Inverter, Decorative Lighting, LCD tunes with alarm.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Modern Appliances and Technologies: LCD and LED TV, Home Security Systems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. S.P. Bali, Consumer Electronics, Pearson Education, 2005 and onwards.
2. R. R. Gulati, "Monochrome and Color Television", New Age International Publisher, 2009 and onwards.
3. B.R. Gupta and V. Singhal, "Consumer Electronics", S.K. Kataria & Sons, 2013 and onwards.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Dhake, "Color Television", McGraw Hill Education, 2004, 2nd Edition and onwards.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE LABORATORY

Subject Code	19SECL55	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	1 (T) + 2(L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to:

- Simulate Various Laws of Electromagnetic Theory
- Simulate discrete time signals and verification of sampling theorem.
- Compute the DFT, Convolution for a discrete signals using MATLAB/Scilab/Octave.
- Simulate IIR /FIR Filters using Matlab/Scilab

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Understand the various concepts of Electric Fields, Electric Flux density.

CO2: Understand the various concepts of transmission lines

CO3: Understand the various concepts analog to digital conversion of signals and Frequency domain sampling of signals.

CO4: Understand the various concepts of Time domain and Frequency domain Computations in DSP.

CO5: Understand design of IIR and FIR filters

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS:

Part A

1. Programs to Calculate
 - i. Calculate Electric Field E at P due to 4 identical charges
 - ii. the total charge enclosed in a volume
 - iii. Electric Flux density ' D ' of a uniform line charge
2. Program to verify the Divergence theorem for the field ' D '
3. Program to find the work involved ' W ' in moving a charge ' Q ' along straight line/ shorter arc of a circle.
4. Program to find potential at point P , Electric Field Intensity E , Flux density D
5. Program to calculate the capacitance of a parallel plate capacitor
6. Program to determine the total voltage as a function of time and position in a loss less transmission line

Part B

7. Verification of sampling theorem.
8. Linear and circular convolution of two given sequences, Commutative, distributive and associative property of convolution.
9. Auto and cross correlation of two sequences and verification of their properties
10. Computation of N point DFT of a given sequence and to plot magnitude and phase spectrum (using DFT equation and verify it by built-in routine).
11. Design and implementation of FIR filter to meet given specifications (using different window techniques).
12. Design and implementation of IIR filter to meet given specifications.

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 marks (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	05
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

CONDUCTION OF PRACTICAL EXAMINATION:

- All laboratory experiments are to be included for practical examination. Question may have sub questions. One question from each part is to be set.
- Students are allowed to pick one experiment from the lot.
- Part A : 20 Marks Part B : 20 Marks Viva :10 Marks Total : 50 Marks

COMPUTER NETWORKS LAB

Subject Code	19SECL56	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	1 (T) + 2(L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Demonstrate operation of network and its management commands.
- Simulate and demonstrate the performance of GSM and CDMA.
- Implement data link layer and transport layer protocols.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

- CO1: Analyze and compare various networking protocols.
- CO2: Demonstrate the working of different concepts of networking.
- CO3: Implement, analyze and evaluate networking protocols in NS2 / NS3.

Description (If any):

- For the experiments below modify the topology and parameters set for the experiment and take multiple rounds of reading and analyze the results available in log files. Plot necessary graphs and conclude. Use NS2/NS3.

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS:

PART A

1. Implement three nodes point – to – point network with duplex links between them. Set the queue size, vary the bandwidth and find the number of packets dropped.
2. Implement transmission of ping messages/trace route over a network topology consisting of 6 nodes and find the number of packets dropped due to congestion.
3. Implement an Ethernet LAN using n nodes and set multiple traffic nodes and plot congestion window for different source / destination.

PART B

Implement the following in Java:

1. Write a program for error detecting code using CRC-CCITT (16- bits).
2. Using TCP/IP sockets, write a client – server program to make the client send the file name and to make the server send back the contents of the requested file if present.
3. Write a program on datagram socket for client/server to display the messages on client side, typed at the server side.
4. Write a program for simple RSA algorithm to encrypt and decrypt the data.

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 marks (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	05
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

CONDUCTION OF PRACTICAL EXAMINATION:

- All laboratory experiments are to be included for practical examination. Question may have sub questions. One question from each part is to be set.
- Students are allowed to pick one experiment from the lot.
- Part A : 20 Marks Part B : 20 Marks Viva :10 Marks Total : 50 Marks

HARDWARE DESCRIPTION LANGUAGES LAB

Subject Code	19SECL57	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	1 (T) + 2(L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Familiarize with the CAD tool to write HDL programs.
- Understand simulation and synthesis of digital design.
- Program FPGAs/CPLDs to synthesize the digital designs.
- Choose either Verilog or VHDL for a given Abstraction level.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

- CO1: Write the Verilog/VHDL programs to simulate Combinational circuits in Dataflow, Behavioral and Gate level Abstractions.
- CO2: Describe sequential circuits like flip flops and counters in Behavioral description and obtain simulation waveforms.
- CO3: Synthesize Combinational and Sequential circuits on programmable ICs and test the hardware.
- CO4: Interface the hardware to the programmable chips and obtain the required output
- CO5: Program FPGAs to synthesize the digital designs.

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS:

Part–A: PROGRAMMING

1. Write Verilog code to realize all the logic gates
2. Write a Verilog program for the following combinational designs
 - a. 2 to 4 decoder
 - b. 8 to 3 (encoder without priority & with priority)
 - c. 8 to 1 multiplexer. d. 4 bit binary to gray converter e. Multiplexer, de-multiplexer, comparator.
3. Write a VHDL and Verilog code to describe the functions of a Full Adder using three modeling styles.
4. Write a Verilog code to model 32 bit ALU using the schematic diagram shown below

- ALU should use combinational logic to calculate an output based on the four bit op-code input.
- ALU should pass the result to the out bus when enable line in high, and tri-state the out bus when the enable line is low.
- ALU should decode the 4 bit op-code according to the example given below.

5. Develop the Verilog code for the following flip-flops, SR, D, JK and T.
6. Design a 4 bit binary, BCD counters (Synchronous reset and Asynchronous reset) and —any sequencell counters, using Verilog code.

Part–B: INTERFACING (at least four of the following must be covered using VHDL/Verilog)

1. Write HDL code to display messages on an alpha numeric LCD display.
2. Write HDL code to interface Hex key pad and display the key code on seven segment display.
3. Write HDL code to control speed, direction of DC / Stepper motor.
4. Write HDL code to accept Analog signal, Temperature sensor and display the data on LCD or Seven segment display.
5. Write HDL code to generate different waveforms (Sine, Square, Triangle, Ramp etc.,) using DAC - change the frequency.
6. Write HDL code to simulate Elevator operation.

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 marks (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	05
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

CONDUCTION OF PRACTICAL EXAMINATION:

- All laboratory experiments are to be included for practical examination. Question may have sub questions. One question from each part is to be set.
- Students are allowed to pick one experiment from the lot.
- Part A : 20 Marks Part B : 20 Marks Viva :10 Marks Total : 50 Marks

ESEP – MOOC

Subject Code	19SEC58	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	0 (L) + 2(S)	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	25	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To improve learnability
- Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study
- Skill development
- Industry readiness
- Increased confidence level

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

- CO1: Improve learnability
- CO2: Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study
- CO3: Develop the skill
- CO4: Industry ready
- CO5: Have more confidence level

ABOUT THE COURSE:

- A common Online MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is offered in Blended mode.
- The MOOC Coordinator will recommend a department specific common course in MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA to all the students of the batch.
- The assessment will be taken by the MOOC Coordinator for 25 Marks at the end of the Course and the remaining 25 marks will be awarded for the Course Completion.
- The student must attend all continuous assessment taken by the MOOC/COURSERA Course Faculty.

ASSESSMENT METHOD FOR MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA COURSE:

- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course has to recommend a common course for the students to register the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for a Specific Title.
- The students have to take all continuous assessment as recommended by the Course Faculty in the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for the internal assessment of 25 Marks.
- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is responsible to conduct Assessment (MCQs) for 25 Marks in the Internal Assessment of 50 Marks.

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Weight-age	Marks
1	Continuous Assessment taken by the MOOC/Coursera Course Faculty	50	25
2	MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Faculty Coordinator has to Conduct Assessment (MCQs / Assignments)	50	25
Total			50

PART-A: EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME-3 (ESEP 3)

Subject Code	19SQA59	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	25	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Learn domain specific knowledge
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART – A

Sentence completion - "a. Using sentence clues. b. Using Hints. c. Structure Words. d. Visualize. e. Pro-active thinking. f. Reactive thinking (signpost words, root words, prefix suffix, sentence structure clues). g. Structure Words. h. Elimination. i. Working Backwards."

Verbal classification - "a. Familiarity. b. Systematic approach. c. Logical thinking. d. Elimination. e. Practice makes perfect."

Time, Speed and Distance - "a. Basics of time, speed and distance b. Relative speed c. Problems based on trains d. Problems based on boats and streams e. Problems based on races"

"Average, Problems on Ages Profit and Loss, Discount"- "a. concept of Average b. Weighted Average c. Problems on Ages (based on average) d. Problems on ages (based on Ratio) e. Concept and Problem-solving technique in Profit and Loss f. Successive Discount"

Syllogism and Venn diagrams, Blood Relations - " a. Syllogisms b. Venn Diagrams – Interpretation c. Venn Diagrams – Solving d. Basic concept and terminology in Blood Relations e. Option Elimination method in Blood Relation"

Logarithms, Algebra - "a. Logarithm concept and problem-solving technique b. Different types of Algebraic expressions c. Different types of Algebraic equations"

Verbal reasoning - "a. Reading techniques. b. Removing assumptions. c. Managing time. d. Honing analytical skills. e. Practicing the right format. f. Learning from mistakes."

Spotting errors - "a. Subject Verb Agreement. b. Right usage of Participles and Infinitives. c. Right usage of Verbs. d. Right usage of Adjectives. e. Checking spelling and punctuation errors."

PART - B

Automatic control system

Signals and system

Assessment pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple choice questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books

1. Quantitative abilities by Arun Sharma
2. Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
3. Verbal and Non-Verbal reasoning by R S Agrawal

PART-B: INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS-3

Subject Code	19SQA59	IA Marks	-
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	-	Total Marks	-
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Have exposure on the latest development

CO2: Acquire new skills

CO3: Become Industry ready

CO4: Have more confidence

CO5: Get additional knowledge

ABOUT THE COURSE:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

NOTE:

- Student has to undergo this course wherever prescribed in the scheme. The certification course must be completed in-campus in offline mode only.
- If a student is unable to produce certificate even after two attempts, such students will be awarded 2 credits with lower grade of passing.

ADVANCED COMMUNICATION

Subject Code	19SEC61	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of the course is to enable students to:

- Understand the mathematical representation of signal, symbol, noise and channels.
- Apply the concept of signal conversion to symbols and signal processing to symbols in transmitter and receiver functional blocks.
- Compute performance issues and parameters for symbol processing and recovery in ideal and corrupted channel conditions.
- Compute performance parameters and mitigate for these parameters in corrupted and distorted channel conditions.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

At the end of this course, the students will be able to

CO1: Associate and apply the concepts of Band pass sampling to well specified signals and channels.

CO2: Analyze and compute performance parameters and transfer rates for low pas and band pass symbol under ideal and corrupted non-band limited channels.

CO3: Test and validate symbol processing and performance parameters at the receiver under ideal and corrupted band limited channels.

CO4: Demonstrate by simulation and emulation that band pass signals subjected to corrupted and distorted symbols in a band limited channel, can be demodulated and estimated at receiver to meet specified performance criteria.

MODULE 1

Bandpass Signal to Equivalent Lowpass: Hilbert Transform, Pre envelopes, Complex envelopes, Canonical representation of bandpass signals, Complex low pass representation of bandpass systems, Complex representation of band pass signals and systems Line codes: Unipolar, Polar, Bipolar (AMI) and Manchester code and their power spectral densities. Overview of HDB3, B3ZS, B6ZS.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Signaling over AWGN Channels- Introduction, Geometric representation of signals, Gram-Schmidt Orthogonalization procedure, Conversion of the continuous AWGN channel into a vector channel, Optimum receivers using coherent detection: ML Decoding, Correlation receiver, matched filter receiver.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Digital Modulation Techniques: Phase shift Keying techniques using coherent detection: generation, detection and error probabilities of BPSK and QPSK, M-ary PSK, M-ary QAM Frequency shift keying techniques using Coherent detection: BFSK generation, detection and error probability. Non-coherent orthogonal modulation techniques: BFSK, DPSK Symbol representation, Block diagrams treatment of Transmitter and Receiver, Probability of error (without derivation of probability of error equation)

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Communication through Band Limited Channels: Digital Transmission through Band limited channels: Digital PAM Transmission through Band limited Channels, Signal design for Band limited Channels: Design of band limited signals for zero ISI–The Nyquist Criterion (statement only), Design of band limited signals with controlled ISI-Partial Response signals, Probability of error for detection of Digital PAM: Probability of error for detection of Digital PAM with Zero ISI, Symbol-by-Symbol detection of data with controlled ISI Channel Equalization: Linear Equalizers (ZFE, MMSE), Adaptive Equalizers.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Principles of Spread Spectrum: Spread Spectrum Communication Systems: Model of a Spread Spectrum Digital Communication System, Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum Systems, Effect of De-spreading on a narrow band Interference, Probability of error (statement only), Some applications of DS Spread Spectrum Signals, Generation of PN Sequences, Frequency Hopped Spread Spectrum, CDMA based on IS-95.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini-project/Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Simon Haykin, "Digital Communication Systems", John Wiley & sons, First Edition, 2014,
2. John G Proakis and Masoud Salehi, "Fundamentals of Communication Systems", 2014 Edition, Pearson Education.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. B.P.Lathi and Zhi Ding, "Modern Digital and Analog communication Systems", Oxford University Press, 4th Edition, 2010.
2. Ian A Glover and Peter M Grant, "Digital Communications", Pearson Education, Third Edition, 2010,.
3. John G Proakis and Masoud Salehi, "Communication Systems Engineering", 2nd Edition, Pearson Education.

VLSI CIRCUITS

Subject Code	19SEC62	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of the course is to enable students to:

- Impart knowledge of MOS transistor theory and CMOS technologies
- Impart knowledge on architectural choices and performance tradeoffs involved in designing and realizing the circuits in CMOS technology
- Cultivate the concepts of subsystem design processes
- Demonstrate the concepts of CMOS testing

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Demonstrate understanding of MOS transistor theory, CMOS fabrication flow and technology scaling.

CO2: Draw the basic gates using the stick and layout diagrams with the knowledge of physical design aspects.

CO3: Interpret Memory elements along with timing considerations

CO4: Demonstrate knowledge of FPGA based system design Interpret testing and testability issues in VLSI Design

CO5: Analyze CMOS subsystems and architectural issues with the design constraints.

MODULE 1

Introduction: A Brief History, MOS Transistors, MOS Transistor Theory, Ideal I-V Characteristics, Non-ideal I-V Effects, DC Transfer Characteristics Fabrication: nMOS Fabrication, CMOS Fabrication [P-well process, N-well process, Twin tub process], BiCMOS Technology.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

MOS and BiCMOS Circuit Design Processes: MOS Layers, Stick Diagrams, Design Rules and Layout. Basic Circuit Concepts: Sheet Resistance, Area Capacitances of Layers, Standard Unit of Capacitance, Some Area Capacitance Calculations, Delay Unit, Inverter Delays, Driving Large Capacitive Loads

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Scaling of MOS Circuits: Scaling Models & Scaling Factors for Device Parameters Subsystem Design Processes: Some General considerations, An illustration of Design Processes, Illustration of the Design Processes- Regularity, Design of an ALU Subsystem, The Manchester Carry-chain and Adder Enhancement Techniques.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Subsystem Design: Some Architectural Issues, Switch Logic, Gate(restoring) Logic, Parity Generators, Multiplexers, The Programmable Logic Array (PLA). FPGA Based Systems: Introduction, Basic concepts, Digital design and FPGA's, FPGA based System design, FPGA architecture, Physical design for FPGA's.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Memory, Registers and Aspects of system Timing- System Timing Considerations, Some commonly used Storage/Memory elements. Testing and Verification: Introduction, Logic Verification, Logic Verification Principles, Manufacturing Test Principles, Design for testability.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/ Solving Challenging Problems/ Case study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. "Basic VLSI Design"- Douglas A. Pucknell& Kamran Eshraghian, PHI 3rd Edition (original Edition – 1994).
2. CMOS VLSI Design- A Circuits and Systems Perspective"- Neil H.E. Weste, David Harris, Ayan Banerjee, 3rd Edition, Pearson Education.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. "FPGA Based System Design"- Wayne Wolf, Pearson Education, 2004, Technology and Engineering.

DIGITAL IMAGE PROCESSING

Subject Code	19SEC631	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Define the fundamental concepts in image processing
- Evaluate techniques followed in image enhancements
- Understand Restoration techniques
- Illustrate image segmentation
- Explain compression algorithms

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Explain fundamentals of image processing

CO2: Compare transformation algorithms

CO3: Perform Contrast enhancement on images.

CO4: Apply algorithms for segmentation

CO5: Apply compression techniques

MODULE 1

Introduction Fundamental Steps in Digital Image Processing, Components of an Image Processing System, Sampling and Quantization, Representing Digital Images (Data structure), Some Basic Relationships Between Pixels- Neighbors and Connectivity of pixels in image, Applications of Image Processing: Medical imaging, Robot vision, Character recognition, Remote Sensing.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Image Enhancement In The Spatial Domain: Some Basic Gray Level Transformations, Histogram Processing, Enhancement Using Arithmetic/Logic Operations, Basics of Spatial Filtering, Smoothing Spatial Filters, Sharpening Spatial Filters, Combining Spatial Enhancement Methods.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Image Enhancement in Frequency Domain: Introduction, Fourier Transform, Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), properties of DFT, Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT), Image filtering in frequency domain. Image Restoration: Image Degradation & Restoration Model, Noise Models, Restoration when noise only, Adaptive filters.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Image Segmentation: Introduction, Detection of isolated points, line detection, Edge detection, Edge linking, Region based segmentation- Region growing, split and merge technique, local processing, regional processing, Hough transform, Segmentation using Threshold.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Image Compression: Introduction, coding Redundancy, Inter-pixel redundancy, image compression model, Lossy and Lossless compression, Huffman Coding, Arithmetic Coding, LZW coding, Transform Coding, Sub-image size selection, blocking, DCT implementation using FFT, Run length coding.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/ Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Rafael C G., Woods R E. and Eddins S L, Digital Image Processing, Prentice Hall, 3rd edition, 2008.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Milan Sonka, "Image Processing, analysis and Machine Vision", Thomson Press India Ltd, Fourth Edition
2. Fundamentals of Digital Image Processing- Anil K. Jain, 2nd Edition, Prentice Hall of India.
3. S. Sridhar, Digital Image Processing, Oxford University Press, 2nd Ed, 2016.

IOT TECHNOLOGY & APPLICATIONS

Subject Code	19SEC632	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Assess the genesis and impact of IoT applications, architectures in real world.
- Illustrate diverse methods of deploying smart objects and connect them to network.
- Compare different Application protocols for IoT.
- Infer the role of Data Analytics and Security in IoT.
- Identify sensor technologies for sensing real world entities and understand the role of IoT in various domains of Industry.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Interpret the impact and challenges posed by IoT networks leading to new architectural models.

CO2: Compare and contrast the deployment of smart objects and the technologies to connect them to network.

CO3: Appraise the role of IoT protocols for efficient network communication.

CO4: Elaborate the need for Data Analytics and Security in IoT.

CO5: Illustrate different sensor technologies for sensing real world entities and identify the applications of IoT in Industry.

MODULE 1

What is IoT, Genesis of IoT, IoT and Digitization, IoT Impact, Convergence of IT and IoT, IoT Challenges, IoT Network Architecture and Design, Drivers Behind New Network Architectures, Comparing IoT Architectures, A Simplified IoT Architecture, The Core IoT Functional Stack, IoT Data Management and Compute Stack.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Smart Objects: The “Things” in IoT, Sensors, Actuators, and Smart Objects, Sensor Networks, Connecting Smart Objects, Communications Criteria, IoT Access Technologies.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

IP as the IoT Network Layer, The Business Case for IP, the need for Optimization, Optimizing IP for IoT, Profiles and Compliances, Application Protocols for IoT, The Transport Layer, IoT Application Transport Methods.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Data and Analytics for IoT, An Introduction to Data Analytics for IoT, Machine Learning, Big Data Analytics Tools and Technology, Edge Streaming Analytics, Network Analytics, Securing IoT, A Brief History of OT Security, Common Challenges in OT Security, How IT and OT Security Practices and Systems Vary, Formal Risk Analysis Structures: OCTAVE and FAIR, The Phased Application of Security in an Operational Environment.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

IoT Physical Devices and Endpoints - Arduino UNO: Introduction to Arduino, Arduino UNO, Installing the Software, Fundamentals of Arduino Programming. IoT Physical Devices and Endpoints - RaspberryPi: Introduction to RaspberryPi, About the RaspberryPi Board: Hardware Layout, Operating Systems on RaspberryPi, Configuring RaspberryPi, Programming RaspberryPi with Python, Wireless Temperature Monitoring System Using Pi, DS18B20 Temperature Sensor, Connecting Raspberry Pi via SSH, Accessing Temperature from DS18B20 sensors, Remote access to RaspberryPi, Smart and Connected Cities, An IoT Strategy for Smarter Cities, Smart City IoT Architecture, Smart City Security Architecture, Smart City Use-Case Examples.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/ Solving Challenging Problems/ Case study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. David Hanes, Gonzalo Salgueiro, Patrick Grossetete, Robert Barton, Jerome Henry, "IoT Fundamentals: Networking Technologies, Protocols, and Use Cases for the Internet of

- Things”, 1stEdition, Pearson Education (Cisco Press Indian Reprint). (ISBN: 9789386873743)
2. Srinivasa K G, “Internet of Things”,CENGAGE Learning India, 2017 Donald Hearn & Pauline Baker: Computer Graphics with OpenGL Version, 3rd / 4th Edition, Pearson Education, 2011.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Vijay Madisetti and ArshdeepBahga, “Internet of Things (A Hands-on-Approach)”, 1stEdition, VPT, 2014. (ISBN: 978-8173719547)
2. Raj Kamal, “Internet of Things: Architecture and Design Principles”, 1st Edition, McGraw Hill Education, 2017. (ISBN: 978-9352605224)

MSP430 MICROCONTROLLER

Subject Code	19SEC633	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Understand MSP430 Architecture
- Addressing Modes & Instruction Set
- Clock System, Interrupts and Operating Modes
- Analog Input-Output and PWM
- Digital Input-Output and Serial Communication

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Explain MSP430 Architecture

CO2: Use Addressing Modes & Instruction Set for programming MSP 430

CO3: Use Clock System, Interrupts and Operating Modes for developing applications.

CO4: Develop applications using Analog Input-Output and PWM in MSP430

CO5: Communicate with external world using Digital Input-Output and Serial Communication

MODULE 1

MSP430 Architecture: Introduction – Where does the MSP430 fit, The outside view, The inside view-Functional block diagram, Memory, Central Processing Unit, Memory Mapped Input and Output, Clock Generator, Exceptions: Interrupts and Resets, MSP430 family.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Addressing Modes & Instruction Set- Addressing Modes, Instruction set, Constant Generator and Emulated Instructions, Program Examples.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Clock System, Interrupts and Operating Modes- Clock System, Interrupts, What happens when an interrupt is requested, Interrupt Service Routines, Low Power Modes of Operation, Watchdog Timer, Basic Timer1, Real Time Clock, Timer-A: TimerBlock, Capture/Compare Channels, Interrupts from Timer-A.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Analog Input-Output and PWM - Comparator-A, ADC10, ADC12, Sigma-Delta ADC, Internal Operational Amplifiers, DAC, Edge Aligned PWM, Simple PWM, Design of PWM.LCD interfacing.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Digital Input-Output and Serial Communication: Parallel Ports, Lighting LEDs, Flashing LEDs, Read Input from a Switch, Toggle the LED state by pressing the push button, LCD interfacing. Asynchronous Serial Communication, Asynchronous Communication with USCI_A, Communications, Peripherals in MSP430, Serial Peripheral Interface.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/ Solving Challenging Problems/ Case study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual)	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. John H Davies, MSP430 Microcontroller Basics, Elsevier 2010

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Cem Unsalan, H Deniz Gurhan, Programmable Microcontrollers with Applications- MSP430 LaunchPad with CCS and Grace, McGraw Hill Education India 2018
2. Nagy Chris, Embedded Systems Design Using the TI MSP430 Series, Elsevier Science.

MACHINE LEARNING

Subject Code	19SEC634	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Define machine learning and problems relevant to machine learning.
- Differentiate supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement learning
- Apply neural networks, Bayes classifier and k nearest neighbor, for problems appear in machine learning.
- Perform statistical analysis of machine learning techniques.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Identify the problems for machine learning.

CO2: Select the either supervised, un supervised or reinforcement learning.

CO3: Explain theory of probability and statistics related to machine learning

CO4: Investigate concept learning, ANN, Bayes classifier, k nearest neighbor, Q, software

CO5: Use proper estimating Hypothesis

MODULE 1

Introduction: Well posed learning problems, Designing a Learning system, Perspective and Issues in Machine Learning. Concept Learning: Concept learning task, Concept learning as search, Find-S algorithm, Version space, Candidate Elimination algorithm, Inductive Bias.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Decision Tree Learning: Decision tree representation, Appropriate problems for decision tree learning, Basic decision tree learning algorithm, hypothesis space search in decision tree learning, Inductive bias in decision tree learning, Issues in decision tree learning.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Artificial Neural Networks: Introduction, Neural Network representation, Appropriate problems, Perceptrons, Back propagation algorithm.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Bayesian Learning: Introduction, Bayes theorem, Bayes theorem and concept learning, ML and LS error hypothesis, ML for predicting probabilities, MDL principle, Naive Bayes classifier, Bayesian belief networks, EM algorithm

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Evaluating Hypothesis: Motivation, estimating hypothesis accuracy, Basics of sampling theorem, General approach for deriving confidence intervals, Difference in error of two hypothesis, Comparing learning algorithms. Instance Based Learning: Introduction, k-nearest neighbor learning, locally weighted regression, radial basis function, cased-based reasoning.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/ Solving Challenging Problems/ Case study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Tom M. Mitchell, Machine Learning, India Edition 2013, McGraw Hill Education.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Trevor Hastie, Robert Tibshirani, Jerome Friedman, h The Elements of Statistical Learning, 2nd edition, springer series in statistics.
2. EthemAlpaydın, Introduction to machine learning, second edition, MIT press.

CRYPTOGRAPHY AND NETWORK SECURITY

Subject Code	19SEC641	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Understand use of Number Theory and Finite Fields network security.
- Explain the concepts of Encryption techniques
- Illustrate key management issues and solutions.
- Familiarize with Cryptography and very essential algorithms

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

- CO1: Define and explain Number Theory and Finite Fields
CO2: Discuss cryptography and its need to various applications
CO3: Define types of ciphers
CO4: Design and develop simple cryptography algorithms
CO5: Use Hash functions

MODULE 1

Basic Concepts of Number Theory and Finite Fields: Divisibility and the divisibility algorithm, Euclidean algorithm, Modular arithmetic, Groups, Rings and Fields, Finite fields of the form $GF(p)$, Polynomial arithmetic, Finite fields of the form $GF(2^n)$.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Classical Encryption Techniques: Symmetric cipher model, Substitution techniques, Transposition techniques, Steganography.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Symmetric Ciphers: The AES Cipher. Pseudo-Random-Sequence Generators and Stream Ciphers: Linear Congruential Generators, Linear Feedback Shift Registers, Design and analysis of stream ciphers, Stream ciphers using LFSRs.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

More number theory: Prime Numbers, Fermat's and Euler's theorem, Primality testing, Chinese Remainder theorem, discrete logarithm. Principles of Public-Key Cryptosystems: The RSA algorithm, Diffie - Hellman Key Exchange, Elliptic Curve Arithmetic, Elliptic Curve Cryptography

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

One-Way Hash Functions: Background, Snefru, N-Hash, MD4, MD5, Secure Hash Algorithm [SHA], One way hash functions using symmetric block algorithms, Using public key algorithms, Choosing a one-way hash functions, Message Authentication Codes. Digital Signature Algorithm, Discrete Logarithm Signature Scheme.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/ Solving Challenging Problems/ Case study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Cryptography and Network Security- William Stallings, Pearson Education, 7th Edition
Cyber Law simplified- Vivek Sood, Mc-GrawHill, 11th reprint, 2013

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Cryptography and Network Security- Behrouz A Forouzan, Debdeep Mukhopadhyay, Mc-GrawHill, 3rd Edition, 2015
2. Cryptography, Network Security and Cyber Laws – Bernard Menezes, Cengage Learning, 2010 edition

OPTICAL FIBER AND NETWORKS

Subject Code	19SEC642	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

After Studying this course, students will

- Understand basics of optical fiber communications
- Learn about transmission characteristics of optical fiber
- Study technology aspects of optical sources

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Obtain the knowledge optical fiber communications

CO2: Understand transmission characteristics of optical fiber.

CO3: Identify and explain working of various optical sources.

CO4: Understand various functions of WDM concepts and components.

CO5: Understand the basic functions of various optical networks.

MODULE 1

Optical fiber Communications: Historical development, The general system, Advantages of optical fiber communication, Optical fiber waveguides: Ray theory transmission, Modes in planar guide, Phase and group velocity, cylindrical fiber: Modes, Step index fibers, Graded index fibers, Single mode fibers, Cutoff wavelength, Mode field diameter, effective refractive index. Fiber Materials, Photonic crystal fibers.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Transmission characteristics of optical fiber: Attenuation, Material absorption losses, Linear scattering losses, Nonlinear scattering losses, Fiber bend loss, Dispersion, Chromatic dispersion, Intermodal dispersion: Multimode step index fiber. Optical Fiber Connectors: Fiber alignment and joint loss, Fiber splices, Fiber connectors, Fiber couplers.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Optical sources: Energy Bands, Direct and Indirect Band gaps, Light Emitting diodes: LED Structures, Light Source Materials, Quantum Efficiency and LED Power, Modulation. Laser Diodes: Modes and Threshold conditions, Rate equation, External Quantum Efficiency, Resonant frequencies, Laser Diode structures and Radiation Patterns: Single mode lasers. Photo detectors: Physical principles of Photodiodes, Photo detector noise, Detector response time. Optical Receiver: Optical Receiver Operation: Error sources, Front End Amplifiers, Receiver sensitivity, Quantum Limit.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

WDM Concepts and Components: Overview of WDM: Operational Principles of WDM, WDM standards, Mach-Zehnder Interferometer Multiplexers, Isolators and Circulators, Fiber grating filters, Dielectric Thin-Film Filters, Diffraction Gratings, Active Optical Components, Tunable light sources, Optical amplifiers: Basic application and Types, Semiconductor optical amplifiers, Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifiers, Raman Amplifiers, Wideband Optical Amplifiers.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Optical Networks: Optical network evolution and concepts: Optical networking terminology, Optical network node and switching elements, Wavelength division multiplexed networks, public telecommunication network overview. Optical network transmission modes, layers and protocols: Synchronous networks, Asynchronous transfer mode, OSI reference model, Optical transport network, Internet protocol, Wavelength routing networks: Routing and wavelength assignment, Optical switching networks: Optical circuit switched networks, packet switched networks, Multiprotocol Label Switching, Optical burst switching networks, Optical network deployment: Long-haul networks, Metropolitan area networks, Access networks, Local area networks.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/ Solving Challenging Problems/ Case study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Gerd Keiser , Optical Fiber Communication, 5th Edition, McGraw Hill 150 Education(India) Private Limited, 2015. ISBN:1-25-900687-5.
2. John M Senior, Optical Fiber Communications, Principles and Practice, 3rd Edition, Pearson Education, 2010, ISBN:978-81-317-3266-3

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Joseph C Palais, Fiber Optic Communication, Pearson Education, 2005, ISBN:0130085103

ADVANCED COMMUNICATION LAB

Subject Code	19SECL65	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	1 (T) + 2(L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Design and demonstrate the digital modulation techniques
- Demonstrate and measure the wave propagation in microstrip antennas
- Characteristics of microstrip devices and measurement of its parameters.
- Model an optical communication system and study its characteristics.
- Simulate the digital communication concepts and compute and display various parameters along with plots/figures.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Determine the characteristics and response of microwave devices and optical waveguide.

CO2: Determine the characteristics of microstrip antennas and devices and compute the parameters associated with it.

CO3: Simulate the digital modulation schemes with the display of waveforms and computation of performance parameters.

CO4: Design and test the digital modulation circuits/systems and display the waveforms.

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS:

PART-A:

1. Time Division Multiplexing and Demultiplexing of two band limited signals.
3. ASK generation and detection
4. FSK generation and detection
5. PSK generation and detection
6. Measurement of frequency, guide wavelength, power, VSWR and attenuation in Microwave test bench.
7. Measurement of propagation loss, bending loss and numerical aperture of an optical fiber.

PART-B:

1. Simulate NRZ, RZ, half-sinusoid and raised cosine pulses and generate eye diagram for binary polar signaling.
2. Simulate the Pulse code modulation and demodulation system and display the waveforms.
3. Simulate FDM Modulation and Demodulation.
4. Simulate the QPSK transmitter and receiver. Plot the signals and its constellation diagram.
5. Test the performance of a binary differential phase shift keying system by simulating the non-coherent detection of binary DPSK.
6. Simulate Dipole, Yagi antennas and study of directivity and gain parameters.

Student activity:

1. Simulate of and study of
 - a. Coupling and isolation characteristics of microstrip directional coupler.

- b. Resonance characteristics of microstrip ring resonator

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 marks (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	5
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

- Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination. **Experiment 1: 20 Marks** (Initial write up: 5 Marks + Conduction of Experiment :10 Marks + Calculation/result: 5 Marks)
- **Experiment 2: 20 Marks** (Initial write up: 5 Marks + Conduction of Experiment :10 Marks + Calculation/result: 5 Marks) **Viva:10 Marks**
- *Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10 Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks.)

VLSI LAB

Subject Code	19SECL66	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	1 (T) + 2(L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Familiarize with the CAD tool to write HDL programs.
- Understand simulation and synthesis of digital design.
- Program FPGAs/CPLDs to synthesize the digital designs.
- Choose either Verilog or VHDL for a given Abstraction level.
- Explore the CAD tool and understand the flow of the Full Custom IC design cycle.
- Learn DRC, LVS and Parasitic Extraction of the various designs.
- Design and simulate the various basic CMOS digital circuits and use them in higher
- Circuits like adders and shift registers using design abstraction concepts.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Write Verilog code and simulate digital circuits.

CO2: Program FPGAs to synthesize the digital designs.

CO3: Write test bench to simulate various digital circuits.

CO4: Design and simulate basic CMOS circuits like inverter and basic Gates.

CO5: Interpret concepts of DC Analysis, AC Analysis and Transient Analysis.

CO6: Use basic amplifiers and further design higher level circuits like operational amplifier and analog/digital converters to meet desired parameters.

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS:

Experiments can be conducted using any of the following or equivalent design tools:

Xilinx/Altera/Model Sim /Cadence/Synopsis/Mentor Graphics/Micro wind/Electric (Open Source) etc. Download the programs on a FPGA board such as Spartan or equivalent and performance testing is to be done.

Part A

1. Write a Verilog program for Inverter and Buffer using switch level.
2. Write a Verilog program for the following combinational designs
 - 2 to 4 decoder
 - 8 to 3 (encoder without priority & with priority)
 - 8 to 1 multiplexer.
 - 4 bit binary to gray converter
 - Multiplexer, de-multiplexer, comparator.
3. Verilog code to describe the functions of a Full Adder. For the above listed designs
 - Write Test Bench for verification Observe the waveform
 - Synthesize the code with technological library with given constraints.

Part B

1. Design an Inverter with given specifications , completing the design flow mentioned below:
a. Draw the schematic and verify the following

- i) DC Analysis
- ii) Transient Analysis

b. Draw the Layout and verify the DRC, ERC

c. Check for LVS

d. Extract RC

a. Draw the schematic for NAND, NOR, AND and OR gates and verify the following

- i) DC Analysis
- ii) AC Analysis
- iii) Transient Analysis

b. Draw the Layout and verify the DRC, ERC

Student activity:

Design a 4-bit R-2R based DAC for the given specification.

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 marks (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	5
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

- Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination. **Experiment 1: 20 Marks** (Initial write up: 5 Marks + Conduction of Experiment :10 Marks + Calculation/result: 5 Marks)
- **Experiment 2: 20 Marks** (Initial write up: 5 Marks + Conduction of Experiment :10 Marks + Calculation/result: 5 Marks) **Viva:10 Marks**
- *Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks.)

IMAGE PROCESSING LAB

Subject Code	19SECL67	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	1 (T) + 2(L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Understand the digital Image Enhancement techniques in Spatial Domain.
- Enhance image quality in Frequency Spatial Domain.
- Apply histogram processing on images.
- Apply Restoration filters on images.
- Apply Morphological image processing techniques.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Write programs to apply Image Enhancement techniques in Spatial Domain.

CO2: Enhance image quality in Frequency Spatial Domain.

CO3: Apply histogram processing on images.

CO4: Apply Restoration filters on images.

CO5: Apply Morphological image processing techniques.

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS:

Experiments are to be carried out using tools Open CV/Python/ SCILAB/MATLAB etc

Experiments/Programs to demonstrate

1. Image representation, gray level basics
2. Point processing and Contrast Stretching, Gray level Slicing
3. Bit plane slicing
4. Histogram Processing.
5. Image Smoothing, Noise removal in spatial Domain.
6. Edge detection Techniques.
7. Frequency domain filters for smoothing, high pass, high boost filtering of images.
8. Image Restoration.
9. Morphological operations.
10. Image Compression

Student activity:

Activity on Image Smoothing, Image compression

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 marks (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	5
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

- Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination. **Experiment 1: 20 Marks** (Initial write up: 5 Marks + Conduction of Experiment :10 Marks + Calculation/result: 5 Marks)
- **Experiment 2: 20 Marks** (Initial write up: 5 Marks + Conduction of Experiment :10 Marks + Calculation/result: 5 Marks) **Viva:10 Marks**
- *Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks.)

ESEP – MINI PROJECT

Subject Code	19SEC68	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4(S)	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	-	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected project topic.
- Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
- Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilizing a systems approach.
- Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral form.
- Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

INSTRUCTIONS/GUIDELINES:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey/ visit industries to finalize the topic of the Project. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected project, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the project work

Students should select a problem which addresses some basic home, office or other real life applications. Students have to collect an International Journal paper on the topics of their interest, prepare a write up and present with suitable demonstration by software or experimental work. Evaluation will be based on relevant topic student has studied, communication skill and reporting/documenting procedure.

SCHEME OF EVALUATION:

CIE marks for the project report and seminar shall be awarded (based on the quality of report and presentation skill, participation in the question-and-answer session by the student) by the committee constituted for the purpose by the Head of the Department. The committee shall consist of 2 faculty members from the department with the senior most acting as the Chairman.

Each student, under the guidance of a Faculty, is required to

- Present the seminar on the selected Project orally and/or through power point slides.
- Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.
- Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.
- The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

Note: This course is a 2-credit course to be completed with only internal assessment mark. The student has to obtain 50% marks (25/50) in the internal assessment to pass the course. There is no semester end examination (SEE).

PART-A: EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME-4 (ESEP 4)

Subject Code	19SQA69	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	25	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability

PART – A

Clocks, calendars, Direction Sence - "a. Concepts on Clocks b. angles between the hand of a clock c. concept of Calendar d. Concept of Leap year, days and date e. Basic concept and Problem solving tecnic for various types of problem in Direction sence"

Critical reasoning- "a. Argument – Identifying the Different Parts (Premise, assumption, conclusion) b. Types of Questions"

Surds, Indices and Simplification - "a. Surds b. Indices c. Simplification exercises"

Set Theory - "a. Set definition and formulas b. Power set c. Sub set d. Set multiplication"

Functions - "a. Roots of a function b. Domain and range c. Problems involving multiple functions"

Cryptarithmic - Problem solving technique on cryptaithmetic

Trigonometry - "a. Heights and distance problems b. Identities, angles c. Simplification"

Letter and Symbol Series, Visual Sequence, Alpha numeric problems - "a. Problem solving tecnic for Letter and Symbol series b. Visual Sequence C. Alpha numeric problems"

Analogy - "a. Synonyms/Antonyms b. Object/ Purpose. c. Source/Product. d. Part/Whole. e. Animal/Habitat. f. Characteristics."

Letter and Email Writing - "a. Types (Formal, Informal, Semi-Formal). b. Formats. c. Samples. d. Practice using the right salutations, greetings, subject line, addresses, conciseness and preciseness."

PART - B

Automatic Control
System Control
Industrial Electronics
Signals & Systems
Data Communication Methods
Microwave Engineering
Microwave Communication

Assessment pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple choice questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books

- Quantitative abilities by Arun Sharma
- Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
- Verbal and Non-Verbal reasoning by R S Agrawal

PART-B: INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS-4

Subject Code	19SQA69	IA Marks	-
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	-	Total Marks	-
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Have exposure on the latest development

CO2: Acquire new skills

CO3: Become Industry ready

CO4: Have more confidence

CO5: Get additional knowledge

ABOUT THE COURSE:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

NOTE:

- Student has to undergo this course wherever prescribed in the scheme. The certification course must be completed in-campus in offline mode only.
- If a student is unable to produce certificate even after two attempts, such students will be awarded 2 credits with lower grade of passing.

POWER ELECTRONICS

Subject Code	19SEC71	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to:

- Understand the construction and working of various power devices.
- Study and analysis of thermistor circuits with different triggering conditions.
- Learn the applications of power devices in controlled rectifiers, converters and inverters.
- Study of power electronics circuits under various load conditions.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Describe the characteristics of different power devices and identify the various applications associated with it.

CO2: Illustrate the working of power circuit as DC-DC converter.

CO3: Illustrate the operation of inverter circuit and static switches.

CO4: Determine the output response of a thyristor circuit with various triggering options.

CO5: Determine the response of controlled rectifier with resistive and inductive loads.

MODULE 1

Introduction - Applications of Power Electronics, Power Semiconductor Devices, Control Characteristics of Power Devices, types of Power Electronic Circuits, Peripheral Effects. Power Transistors: Power BJTs: Steady state characteristics. Power MOSFETs: device operation, switching characteristics, IGBTs: device operation, output and transfer characteristics, di/dt and dv/dt limitations.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Thyristors - Introduction, Principle of Operation of SCR, Static Anode-Cathode Characteristics of SCR, Two transistor model of SCR, Gate Characteristics of SCR, Turn-ON Methods, Turn-OFF Mechanism, Turn-OFF Methods: Natural and Forced Commutation – Class A and Class B types, Gate Trigger Circuit: Resistance Firing Circuit, Resistance capacitance firing circuit, UJT Firing Circuit.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Controlled Rectifiers - Introduction, Principle of Phase-Controlled Converter Operation, Single-Phase Full Converter with RL Load, Single-Phase Dual Converters, Single-Phase Semi Converter with RL load. AC Voltage Controllers - Introduction, Principles of ON-OFF Control, Principle of Phase Control, Single phase controllers with resistive and inductive loads.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

DC-DC Converters - Introduction, principle of step-down operation and it's analysis with RL load, principle of step-up operation, Step-up converter with a resistive load, Performance parameters, Converter classification, Switching mode regulators: Buck regulator, Boost regulator, Buck-Boost Regulators, Chopper circuit design.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Pulse Width Modulated Inverters- Introduction, principle of operation, performance parameters, Single phase bridge inverters, voltage control of single-phase inverters, current source inverters, Variable DC-link inverter, Boost inverter, Inverter circuit design. Static Switches: Introduction, Single phase AC switches, DC Switches, Solid state relays, Microelectronic relays.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini-project/Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Mohammad H Rashid, Power Electronics, Circuits, Devices and Applications, 3rd/4th Edition, Pearson Education Inc, 2014, ISBN: 978-93-325-1844-5.
2. M.D Singh and K B Khanchandani, Power Electronics, 2nd Edition, Tata Mc-Graw Hill, 2009, ISBN: 0070583897

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. L. Umanand, Power Electronics, Essentials and Applications, John Wiley India Pvt. Ltd, 2009.
2. Dr. P. S. Bimbhra, —Power Electronics, Khanna Publishers, Delhi, 2012.
3. P.C. Sen, —Modern Power Electronics, S Chand & Co New Delhi, 2005.
4. Earl Gose, Richard Johnsonbaugh, Steve Jost, Pattern Recognition and Image Analysis, ePub eBook.

DATA ACQUISITION AND PLC

Subject Code	19SEC721	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to:

- Understand Basics and types of DACs
- Understand Basics and types of ADCs
- Understand the concepts of PLC programming and its operations.
- Design the connectivity between various modules in a system with PLC.
- To create ladder diagrams from process control descriptions.
- Understand various types of PLC registers and apply PLC Timers and Counters for the control of industrial processes. Understand PLC functions, Data Handling Function.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Understand different types of ADCs and DACs

CO2: Gain knowledge on Programmable Logic Controllers.

CO3: Understand different types of Devices to which PLC input and output modules are connected.

CO4: Create ladder diagrams from process control descriptions.

CO5: Apply PLC timers and counters for the control of industrial processes.

MODULE 1

Data Acquisition Systems: Types of instrumentation systems, Components of analog data acquisition system, Digital data acquisition system, Use of recorders in digital systems, Digital recording systems. Data Converters: Digital to Analog Converters: Basic DAC techniques, Weighted Resistor DAC, R – 2R Ladder DAC, DAC 0800. DAC parameters Interfacing DACs with Microprocessors.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Analog to Digital Converters: Functional diagram of ADC, Flash ADC, and Counter type ADC, Successive approximation ADC, Dual slope ADC. ADC 0809, DAC/ADC specifications. Interfacing ADCs with Microprocessors. Sample and Hold Circuits.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Introduction to PLC Technical Definition, Advantages, Characteristic Functions, Chronological Evolution, Types, Unitary PLC, Modular PLC, SMEEI PLC, Medium PLC, Large PLC, Block Diagram Of PLC, Input / Output Section, Processor Section, Power Supply, Memory, Central Processing Unit, Processor Software / Executive Software, Multitasking,

Languages, Ladder Language. Bit Logic Instructions Introduction, Input and Output Contact Program, Symbols, Numbering System Of Inputs And Outputs, Program Format, Introduction To Logic, Equivalent Ladder Diagram Of - AND Gate, OR Gate, NOT Gate, XOR Gate, NAND Gate, NOR Gate, Equivalent Ladder Diagram To Demonstrate De Morgan Theorem, Ladder Design.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

PLC Timers And Counters Timer and Its Classification, Characteristics of PLC Timer, Functions In Timer, Resetting – Retentive And Non-Retentive, Classification Of PLC Timer, On Delay, And Off Delay Timers, Timer-On Delay, Timer Off Delay, Retentive And Non-Retentive Timers, Format of a Timer Instruction. PLC Counter, Operation of PLC Counter, Counter Parameters, Counter Instructions. Overview, Count Up (CTU), Count Down (CTD). Advanced Instructions Comparison Instructions, Addressing Data Files, Format of Logical Address and Addressing Format for Micro logic System, Different Addressing Types. Data Movement Instructions.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Logical Instructions Mathematical Instructions and its Features, Special Mathematical Instructions, Scale with Parameters or SCP Instruction. Data Handling Instructions and its Features, Program Flow Control Instructions, Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) Instruction. PLC I/O Modules And Power Supply Classification Of I/O, I/O System Overview, Practical I/O System and its mapping, Addressing Local and Expansion I/O, Input-Output Systems, Direct I/O Parallel I/O Systems Serial I/O Systems, Sinking And Sourcing, Sourcing and Sinking in PLC Interfacing, Discrete Input Module, Discrete DC Input Module, Discrete AC Input Module, Rectifier with Filter, Threshold Detection, Isolation, Logic Section, Discrete Output Modules, Advantages and Disadvantages Of Output Modules, Types of Analog Input Module.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini-project/Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Madhuchhanda Mitra and Samarjit Sen Gupta, —Programmable Logic Controllers and Industrial Automation, Penram International Publishing (India) Pvt. Ltd., 2007. ISBN: 81-87972-17-3.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Garry Dunning, —Introduction to Programmable Logic Controllers, 2nd Edition, Delmar Thomson Learning, 2001. ISBN: 981-240-625-5.
2. M. Chidambaram, —Computer Control of Processes, CRC Press, 2002. ISBN:0849310105.

DIGITAL SWITCHING SYSTEMS

Subject Code	19SEC722	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Understand the basics of telecommunication networks and digital transmission of data.
- Study about the evolution of switching systems and the digital switching.
- Study about the telecommunication traffic and its measurements.
- Learn the technologies associated with the data switching operations and understand the use of software for the switching and its maintenance

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Describe the electromechanical switching systems

CO2: Compare electromechanical switching systems with the digital switching.

CO3: Determine the telecommunication traffic and its measurements.

CO4: Define the technologies associated with the data switching operations.

CO5: Describe the software aspects of switching systems and its maintenance.

MODULE 1

DEVELOPMENT OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS: Network structure, Network services, terminology, Regulation, Standards. Introduction to telecommunications transmission, Power levels, four wire circuits, Digital transmission, FDM, TDM, PDH and SDH.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Evolution of switching systems: Introduction, Message switching, Circuit switching, Functions of switching systems, Distribution systems, Basics of crossbar systems, electronic switching. DIGITAL SWITCHING SYSTEMS: Switching system hierarchy, Evolution of digital switching systems, Stored program control switching systems, Building blocks of a digital switching system, Basic call processing.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Telecommunications traffic: Introduction, Unit of traffic, Congestion, Traffic measurement, Mathematical model, lost call systems, Queuing systems. SWITCHING SYSTEMS: Introduction, Single stage networks, Grading, Design of progressive grading, Skipped Grading, Homogeneous Grading, Traffic capacity of grading, Application of Grading, two stage Switching network, Link Systems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

TIME DIVISION SWITCHING: Introduction, space and time switching, Time switching networks, Synchronization. Switching system software: Introduction, Basic software architecture, Software architecture for level 1to 3 control, Digital switching system software classification, Call models, Software linkages during call, Feature flow diagram, Feature interaction.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Module 5

Maintenance of digital switching system: Introduction, Software maintenance, Interface of a typical digital switching system central office, System outage and its impact on digital switching system reliability, Impact of software patches on digital switching system maintainability. A generic digital switching system model: Introduction, Hardware architecture, Software architecture, Recovery strategy, Simple call through a digital system, Common characteristics of digital switching systems. Reliability analysis.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini-project/Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks.

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Telecommunication and Switching, Traffic and Networks - J E Flood: Pearson Education, 2002.
2. Digital Switching Systems, Syed R. Ali, TMH Ed 2002.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Digital Telephony - John C Bellamy: Wiley India Pvt. Ltd, 3rd Ed, 2008.

MEDICAL ELECTRONICS

Subject Code	19SEC723	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- To gain knowledge about the various physiological parameters both electrical and non-electrical and the methods of recording and also the method of transmitting these parameters
- To study about the various assist devices used in the hospitals
- To gain knowledge about equipment used for physical medicine and the various recently developed diagnostic and therapeutic techniques.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Know the human body electro- physiological parameters and recording of bio-potentials

CO2: Comprehend the non-electrical physiological parameters and their measurement – body temperature, blood pressure, pulse, blood cell count, blood flow meter etc.

CO3: Interpret the various assist devices used in the hospitals viz. pacemakers, defibrillators, dialyzers and ventilators

CO4: Comprehend physical medicine methods eg. ultrasonic, shortwave, microwave surgical diathermies, and bio-telemetry principles and methods

CO5: Know about recent trends in medical instrumentation

MODULE 1

Bioelectric signals; Cell characteristics. Bio-electric potential: Origin, Resting and action potential, depolarization and repolarization, propagation of action potentials, ECG, EEG and EMG waveforms with typical characteristics. Electrodes: Types, Electrodes used for ECG, EEG and EMG. Selection of physiological transducers.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Basic recording systems. Block diagram of ECG, isolated preamplifier, ECG leads, effects of artefacts on ECG recordings, Multichannel ECG machine, Block diagram of EEG machine, 10-20 electrode placement system for EEG, and Evoked potential. Working of EMG with block diagram. Applications of ECG, EEG, EMG and ERG recordings.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Assist Devices: Cardiac pacemakers, DC Defibrillator, Dialyzer, Ventilators, Magnetic Resonance Imaging Systems, Ultrasonic Imaging Systems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Blood constituents- calculation of size of cells- MCV, MCH, MCHC, MPV, RDW& PDW, Blood cell counter- Coulter's method and Dark field method, Digital pH meter, Spectrophotometer, Oximetry – fingertip oximeter. Features of Blood flow meters. Ultrasonic Doppler-shift based FHR measurement. BP measurement-systolic & diastolic pressure, direct method and indirect methods, BP measurement using ultrasonic doppler shift method, advantages & disadvantages. Rheographic method of indirect blood flow measurement.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

X-Rays- properties, X-ray imaging machine, applications, advantages and disadvantages. Computerized tomography- basic principle, block diagram of a typical CT imaging system, advantages, disadvantages and applications of CT imaging. Magnetic resonance imaging principles of NMR imaging, basic components of a typical NMR imaging system, applications, advantages and disadvantages of magnetic resonance imaging. Ultra-sonic imaging-properties of ultrasonic waves, basic pulse echo apparatus. Concept and features of patient monitoring system.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Leslie Cromwell, Biomedical Instrumentation and Measurement, Prentice Hall of India, New Delhi, 2007.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Khandpur, R.S., Handbook of Biomedical Instrumentation, TATA McGraw-Hill, New Delhi, 2003.
2. John G.Webster, Medical Instrumentation Application and Design, 3rd Edition, Wiley India Edition, 2007
3. Joseph J.Carr and John M.Brown, Introduction to Biomedical Equipment Technology, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 2004.

INTRODUCTION TO NEMS

Subject Code	19SEC724	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- To understand the basic components of MEMS and NEMS
- To study, design the MEMS and NEMS based devices

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Understand Microsensors and Actuators

CO2: Understand Transduction platforms

CO3: Understand Micromachining and MEMS materials

CO4: Understand Integration of MEMS devices

CO5: Understand NEMS

MODULE 1

Introduction: Miniaturization, Integrated Circuits, Microsensors, Microactuators, Thermal MEMS, Micro-Opto Electro mechanical Systems (MOEMS), Magnetic MEMS, Microfluidics, RF MEMS, Packaging. Micro sensors & actuators: Principle of sensing and actuation, silicon capacity sensors, piezo-resistive sensors, electrostatic comb drive, magnetic microrelay, piezo-ink jet printer, micromirrors, array sensors, microgrippers, gyroscopes, micro beams and cantilever.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Transduction platforms: Introduction - Conductometric and Capacitive Transducers, Optical Waveguide based Transducers, Electrochemical Transducers, Solid State Transducers - Schottky Diode based Transducers - p-n Diodes or Bipolar Junction based Transducers - MOS Capacitor based Transducers, Acoustic Wave Transducers - Cantilever based Transducers - Quartz Crystal Microbalance - Film Bulk Acoustic Wave Resonator.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Micromachining: Types of wafers, orientation, Photolithography, etching methods, Silicon polishing, surface and bulk micromachining, thin film deposition techniques sputtering, CVD, epitaxial growth, thermal oxidation, wafer bonding. MEMS materials: Single crystal silicon, poly silicon, SiO₂, SiN, Germanium based materials, metals, SiC, diamond III-V materials, piezoelectric materials.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Integration of MEMS devices: Microsystem packaging, packaging technologies, reliability, failure mechanisms, CMOS, stability, transient properties and performance, traceability and calibration, scaling effects, signal amplifiers, transmitters, signal conditioning, basics of control theory, case studies.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Nanoelectromechanical systems (NEMS): Introduction- Nano machining of NEMS based upon electron beam lithography, Nano electromechanical systems fabrication, nano imprint lithography, polymeric nano fiber templates, focused ion beam doping and wet chemical etching, stencil lithography and sacrificial etching, large scale integration, future challenges, applications.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Ho, C. M., & Tai, Y. C. (1998). Micro-electro-mechanical-systems (MEMS) and fluid flows. Annual review of fluid mechanics, 30, 579-612.
2. Judy, J. W. (2001). Microelectromechanical systems (MEMS): fabrication, design and applications. Smart materials and Structures, 10(6), 1115.
3. Lyshevski, S. E. (2018). MEMS and NEMS: systems, devices, and structures. CRC press.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Yang, C. K. (2012). From mems to nems: Scaling cantilever sensors.
2. Ekinici, K. L. (2005). Electromechanical transducers at the nanoscale: actuation and sensing of motion in nanoelectromechanical systems (NEMS). *small*, 1(8-9), 786-797.
3. Miranda, D. R., Moreno, R., & Iapichino, G. (1997). Nine equivalents of nursing manpower use score (NEMS). *Intensive care medicine*, 23(7), 760-765.

PATTERN RECOGNITION

Subject Code	19SEC731	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Introduce mathematical tools needed for Pattern Recognition
- Impart knowledge about the fundamentals of Pattern Recognition.
- Provide knowledge of recognition, decision making and statistical learning problems
- Introduce parametric and non-parametric techniques, supervised learning and clustering concepts of pattern recognition

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify areas where Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning can offer a solution.

CO2: Describe the strength and limitations of some techniques used in computational

CO3: Machine Learning for classification, regression and density estimation problems

CO4: Describe genetic algorithms, validation methods and sampling techniques

CO5: Describe and model data to solve problems in regression and classification · Implement learning algorithms for supervised tasks

MODULE 1

Introduction: Importance of pattern recognition, Features, Feature Vectors, and Classifiers, Supervised, Unsupervised, and Semi-supervised learning, Introduction to Bayes Decision Theory, Discriminant Functions and Decision Surfaces, Gaussian PDF and Bayesian Classification for Normal Distributions.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Data Transformation and Dimensionality Reduction: Introduction, Basis Vectors, The Karhunen Loeve (KL) Transformation, Singular Value Decomposition, Independent Component Analysis (Introduction only). Nonlinear Dimensionality Reduction, Kernel PCA.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Estimation of Unknown Probability Density Functions: Maximum Likelihood Parameter Estimation, Maximum a Posteriori Probability estimation, Bayesian Interference, Maximum Entropy Estimation, Mixture Models, Naive-Bayes Classifier, The Nearest Neighbor Rule.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Linear Classifiers: Introduction, Linear Discriminant Functions and Decision Hyperplanes, The Perceptron Algorithm, Mean Square Error Estimate, Stochastic Approximation of LMS Algorithm, Sum of Error Estimate.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Nonlinear Classifiers: The XOR Problem, The two Layer Perceptron, Three Layer Perceptron, Back propagation Algorithm, Basic Concepts of Clustering, Introduction to Clustering, Proximity Measures.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Pattern Recognition: Sergios Theodoridis, Konstantinos Koutroumbas, Elsevier India Pvt. Ltd 4th edition.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. The Elements Of Statistical Learning: Trevor Hastie, Springer-Verlag New York, LLC 2009.
2. Pattern Classification: Richard O. Duda, Peter E. Hart, David G. Stork. John Wiley & Sons, 2012.
3. Pattern Recognition And Image Analysis: Earl Gose, Richard Johnsonbaugh, Steve Jost

COMPUTER VISION

Subject Code	19SEC732	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- This course will enable students to
- To understand shape and region analysis.
- To understand Hough Transform and its applications to detect lines, circles, ellipses.
- To understand three-dimensional image analysis techniques.
- To study some applications of computer vision algorithms.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Implement fundamental image processing techniques required for computer vision.

CO2: Perform shape analysis.

CO3: Implement boundary tracking techniques.

CO4: Apply chain codes and other region descriptors.

CO5: Apply 3D vision techniques. Implement motion related techniques.

MODULE 1

Image processing foundations: Review of image processing techniques – classical filtering operations – thresholding techniques – edge detection techniques – corner and interest point detection – mathematical morphology – texture.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Shapes and regions: Binary shape analysis – connectedness – object labeling and counting – size filtering – distance functions – skeletons and thinning – deformable shape analysis – boundary tracking procedures – active contours – shape models and shape recognition – centroidal profiles – handling occlusion – boundary length measures – boundary descriptors – chain codes – Fourier descriptors – region descriptors – moments.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Hough transform: Line detection – Hough Transform (HT) for line detection – foot-of-normal method – line localization – line fitting – RANSAC for straight line detection – HT based circular object detection – accurate center location – speed problem – ellipse detection – Case study: Human Iris location – hole detection – generalized Hough Transform (GHT) – spatial matched filtering – GHT for ellipse detection – object location – GHT for feature collation.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

3D VISION AND MOTION: Methods for 3D vision – projection schemes – shape from shading – photometric stereo – shape from texture – shape from focus – active range finding – surface representations – point-based representation – volumetric representations – 3D object recognition – 3D reconstruction – introduction to motion – triangulation – bundle adjustment – translational alignment – parametric motion – spline-based motion – optical flow – layered motion.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

APPLICATIONS: Photo album – Face detection – Face recognition – Eigen faces – Active appearance and 3D shape models of faces Application: Surveillance – foreground-background separation – particle filters – Chamfer matching, tracking, and occlusion – combining views from multiple cameras – human gait analysis Application: In-vehicle vision system: locating roadway – road markings – identifying road signs – locating pedestrians.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project /Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. D. L. Baggio et al., —Mastering Open CV with Practical Computer Vision Projects , Packt Publishing, 2012.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. E. R. Davies, —Computer & Machine Vision , Fourth Edition, Academic Press, 2012.
2. Jan Erik Solem, —Programming Computer Vision with Python: Tools and algorithms for analyzing images , O'Reilly Media, 2012.
3. Mark Nixon and Alberto S. Aquado, —Feature Extraction & Image Processing for Computer Vision , Third Edition, Academic Press, 2012.
4. R. Szeliski, —Computer Vision: Algorithms and Applications , Springer 2011.
5. Simon J. D. Prince, —Computer Vision: Models, Learning, and Inference , Cambridge University Press, 2012.

MULTIMEDIA COMMUNICATION

Subject Code	19SEC733	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Gain fundamental knowledge in understanding the basics of different multimedia networks and applications.
- Understand digitization principle techniques required to analyze different media types.
- Analyze compression techniques required to compress text and image and gain knowledge of DMS. Analyze compression techniques required to compress audio and video.
- Gain fundamental knowledge about multimedia communication across different networks.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Understand basics of different multimedia networks and applications.

CO2: Understand different compression techniques to compress audio and video.

CO3: Describe multimedia Communication across Networks.

CO4: Analyze different media types to represent them in digital form.

CO5: Compress different types of text and images using different compression techniques.

MODULE 1

Multimedia Communications: Introduction, Multimedia information representation, multimedia networks: Telephone networks, Data networks, Broadcast television networks, Integrated services digital networks, Broadband multi service network. Multimedia applications: Interpersonal application, Interactive application over the internet, Entertainment application. Application and networking terminology: Media types, communication modes, network types, multipoint conferencing, network QoS.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Information Representation: Introduction, Digitization principles: analog signals, encoder design, decoder design. Text: unformatted text, formatted text, hypertext. Images: graphics, digitized documents, digitized pictures. Audio: PCM speech, CD-quality audio, synthesized audio. Video: broad band television, digital video.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Text and image compression: Introduction, Compression principles: source encoders and destination decoders, lossless and lossy compression, entropy encoding, source encoding. Text compression: static and dynamic Huffman coding, arithmetic coding. Image Compression.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Audio and video compression: Introduction, Audio compression: Differential pulse code modulation, adaptive differential PCM, adaptive predictive coding. Video Compression: video compression principles, H.261, H.263, MPEG, MPEG-1.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Multimedia Communication Across Networks: Packet audio/video in the network environment, Video transport across generic networks, Multimedia Transport across ATM Networks.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Fred Halsall, —Multimedia Communications, Pearson education, 2001 ISBN - 9788131709948.
2. K. R. Rao, Zoran S. Bojkovic, Dragorad A. Milovanovic, —Multimedia Communication Systems, Pearson education, 2004. ISBN -9788120321458

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Raifsteinmetz, KlaraNahrstedt, —Multimedia: Computing, Communications and Applications, Pearson education, 2002. ISBN -9788177584417

INTRODUCTION TO MEMS

Subject Code	19SEC734	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To understand basics of MEMS and Microsystems
- To understand Working Principles of Microsystems
- To understand Engineering Mechanics for Microsystems Design:
- To understand Scaling Laws in Miniaturization:
- To study some Overview of Micromanufacturing

COURSE OUTCOMES:

The students should be able to:

CO1: Define what are MEMS and Microsystems

CO2: Describe the Working Principles of Microsystems

CO3: Explain Engineering Mechanics for Microsystems Design:

CO4: Explain Scaling Laws in Miniaturization:

CO5: Describe the Overview of Micromanufacturing

MODULE 1

Overview of MEMS and Microsystems: MEMS and Microsystem, Typical MEMS and Microsystems Products, Evolution of Microfabrication, Microsystems and Microelectronics, Multidisciplinary Nature of Microsystems, Miniaturization. Applications and Markets.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Working Principles of Microsystems: Introduction, Micro sensors, Micro actuation, MEMS with Micro actuators, Micro accelerometers, Microfluidics. Engineering Science for Microsystems Design and Fabrication: Introduction, Molecular Theory of Matter and Inter-molecular Forces, Plasma Physics, Electrochemistry

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Engineering Mechanics for Microsystems Design: Introduction, Static Bending of Thin Plates, Mechanical Vibration, Thermo mechanics, Fracture Mechanics, Thin Film Mechanics, and Overview on Finite Element Stress Analysis.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Scaling Laws in Miniaturization: Introduction, Scaling in Geometry, Scaling in Rigid-Body Dynamics, Scaling in Electrostatic Forces, Scaling in Fluid Mechanics, Scaling in Heat Transfer.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Overview of Micro manufacturing: Introduction, Bulk Micro manufacturing, Surface Micromachining, The LIGA Process, Summary on Micro manufacturing.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Tai-Ran Hsu, MEMS and Micro systems: Design, Manufacture and Nanoscale Engineering, 2nd Ed, Wiley.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Hans H. Gatzert, Volker Saile, Jurg Leuthold, Micro and Nano Fabrication: Tools and Processes, Springer, 2015.
2. Dilip Kumar Bhattacharya, Brajesh Kumar Kaushik, Microelectromechanical Systems (MEMS), Cengage Learning.

DSP ALGORITHMS AND ARCHITECTURE

Subject Code	19SEC741	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Figure out the knowledge and concepts of digital signal processing techniques.
- Understand the computational building blocks of DSP processors and its speed issues.
- Understand the various addressing modes, peripherals, interrupts and pipelining structure of TMS320C54xx processor.
- Learn how to interface the external devices to TMS320C54xx processor in various modes.
- Understand basic DSP algorithms with their implementation.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Comprehend the knowledge and concepts of digital signal processing techniques.

CO2: Apply the knowledge of DSP computational building blocks to achieve speed in DSP architecture or processor.

CO3: Apply knowledge of various types of addressing modes, interrupts, peripherals and pipelining of TMS320C54xx processor.

CO4: Develop basic DSP algorithms using DSP processors.

CO5: Discuss about synchronous serial interface and multi-channel buffered serial port (McBSP) of DSP device.

MODULE 1

Introduction to Digital Signal Processing: Introduction, A Digital Signal – Processing System, The Sampling Process, Discrete Time Sequences, Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), Linear Time-Invariant Systems, Digital Filters, Decimation and Interpolation. Computational Accuracy in DSP Implementations: Number Formats for Signals and Coefficients in DSP Systems, Dynamic Range and Precision, Sources of Error in DSP Implementation.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Architectures for Programmable Digital Signal – Processing Devices: Introduction, Basic Architectural Features, DSP Computational Building Blocks, Bus Architecture and Memory, Data Addressing Capabilities, Address Generation Unit, Programmability and Program Execution, Speed Issues, Features for External Interfacing.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Programmable Digital Signal Processors: Introduction, Commercial Digital Signal-processing Devices, Data Addressing Modes of TMS320C54XX, Memory Space of TMS320C54xx Processors, Program Control. Detail Study of TMS320C54X & 54xx Instructions and Programming, On – Chip Peripherals, Interrupts of TMS320C54XX Processors, Pipeline Operation of TMS320C54xx Processor.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Module 4

Implementation of Basic DSP Algorithms: Introduction, The Q – notation, FIR Filters, IIR Filters, Interpolation and Decimation Filters (one example in each case). Implementation of FFT Algorithms: Introduction, An FFT Algorithm for DFT Computation, Overflow and Scaling, Bit – Reversed Index. Generation & Implementation on the TMS320C54xx.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Interfacing Memory and Parallel I/O Peripherals to Programmable DSP Devices: Introduction, Memory Space Organization, External Bus Interfacing Signals. Memory Interface, Parallel I/O Interface, Programmed I/O, Interrupts and I/O Direct Memory Access (DMA). Interfacing and Applications of DSP Processors: Introduction, Synchronous Serial Interface, A CODEC Interface Circuit, DSP Based Bio-telemetry Receiver, A Speech Processing System, An Image Processing System.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Charles R. Severance, “Python for Everybody: Exploring Data Using Python 3”, 1st Edition, CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform, 2016.
2. (http://do1.drchuck.com/pythonlearn/EN_us/pythonlearn.pdf) (Chapters 1 – 13, 15)
3. Allen B. Downey, "Think Python: How to Think Like a Computer Scientist", 2ndEdition, Green Tea Press, 2015.
4. (<http://greenteapress.com/thinkpython2/thinkpython2.pdf>) (Chapters 15, 16, 17)(Download pdf files from the above links)

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Charles Dierbach, "Introduction to Computer Science Using Python", 1st Edition, Wiley India Pvt Ltd. ISBN-13: 978-8126556014
2. Mark Lutz, “Programming Python”, 4th Edition, O’Reilly Media, 2011.ISBN-13: 978-9350232873
3. Wesley J Chun, “Core Python Applications Programming”, 3rdEdition,Pearson Education India, 2015. ISBN-13: 978-9332555365
4. Roberto Tamassia, Michael H Goldwasser, Michael T Goodrich, “Data Structures and Algorithms in Python”,1stEdition, Wiley India Pvt Ltd, 2016. ISBN-13: 978- 8126562176
5. ReemaThareja, “Python Programming using problem solving approach”, Oxford university press, 2017

OBJECT ORIENTED PROGRAMMING USING C++

Subject Code	19SEC742	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Define Encapsulation, Inheritance and Polymorphism.
- Solve the problem with object-oriented approach.
- Analyze the problem statement and build object-oriented system model.
- Describe the characters and behavior of the objects that comprise a system.
- Explain function overloading, operator overloading and virtual functions.
- Discuss the advantages of object-oriented programming over procedure-oriented programming.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Explain the basics of Object-Oriented Programming concepts.

CO2: Apply the object initialization and destroy concept using constructors and destructors.

CO3: Apply the concept of polymorphism to implement compile time polymorphism in programs by using overloading methods and operators.

CO4: Use the concept of inheritance to reduce the length of code and evaluate the usefulness.

CO5: Apply the concept of run time polymorphism by using virtual functions, overriding functions and abstract class in programs. Use I/O operations and file streams in programs.

MODULE 1

Beginning with C++ and its features: What is C++?, Applications and structure of C++ program, Different Data types, Variables, Different Operators, expressions, operator overloading and control structures in C++

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Functions, classes and Objects: Functions, Inline function, function overloading, friend and virtual functions, Specifying a class, C++ program with a class, arrays within a class, memory allocation to objects, array of objects, members, pointers to members and member functions.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Constructors, Destructors and Operator overloading: Constructors, Multiple constructors in a class, copy constructor, Dynamic constructor, Destructors, defining operator overloading, Overloading Unary and binary operators, Manipulation of strings using operators.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Module 4

Inheritance, Pointers, Virtual Functions, Polymorphism: Derived Classes, Single, multilevel, multiple inheritance, Pointers to objects and derived classes, this pointer, Virtual and pure virtual functions.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Streams and working with files: C++ streams and stream classes, formatted and unformatted I/O operations, Output with manipulators, Classes for file stream operations, opening and closing a file, EOF.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Object Oriented Programming with C++, E. Balaguruswamy, TMH, 6th Edition, 2013.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Object Oriented Programming using C++, Robert Lafore, Galgotia publication 2010.

ADVANCED JAVA PROGRAMMING

Subject Code	19SEC743	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Identify the need for advanced Java concepts like Enumerations and Collections
- Construct client-server applications using Java socket API
- Make use of JDBC to access database through Java Programs
- Adapt servlets to build server-side programs
- Demonstrate the use of JavaBeans to develop component-based Java software

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Interpret the need for advanced Java concepts like enumerations and collections in developing modular and efficient programs

CO2: Build client-server applications and TCP/IP socket programs

CO3: Illustrate database access and details for managing information using the JDBC API

CO4: Describe how servlets fit into Java-based web application architecture

CO5: Develop reusable software components using Java Beans

MODULE 1

Enumerations, Autoboxing and Annotations(metadata): Enumerations, Enumeration fundamentals, the values() and valueOf() Methods, java enumerations are class types, enumerations Inherits Enum, example, type wrappers, Autoboxing, Autoboxing and Methods, Autoboxing/Unboxing occurs in Expressions, Autoboxing/Unboxing, Boolean and character values, Autoboxing/Unboxing helps prevent errors, A word of Warning. Annotations, Annotation basics, specifying retention policy, Obtaining Annotations at run time by use of reflection, Annotated element Interface, Using Default values, Marker Annotations, Single Member annotations, Built-In annotations.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

The collections and Framework: Collections Overview, Recent Changes to Collections, The Collection Interfaces, The Collection Classes, accessing a collection Via an Iterator, Storing User Defined Classes in Collections, The Random Access Interface, Working with Maps, Comparators, The Collection Algorithms, Why Generic Collections? The legacy Classes and Interfaces, Parting Thoughts on Collections

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

String Handling :The String Constructors, String Length, Special String Operations, String Literals, String Concatenation, String Concatenation with Other Data Types, String Conversion and toString() Character Extraction, charAt(), getChars(), getBytes() toCharArray(), String Comparison, equals() and equalsIgnoreCase(), regionMatches() startsWith() and endsWith(), equals() Versus == , compareTo() Searching Strings, Modifying a String, substring(), concat(), replace(), trim(), Data Conversion Using valueOf(), Changing the Case of Characters Within a String, Additional String Methods, StringBuffer , StringBuffer Constructors, length() and capacity(), ensureCapacity(), setLength(), charAt() and setCharAt(), getChars(),append(), insert(), reverse(), delete() and deleteCharAt(), replace(), substring(), Additional StringBuffer Methods, StringBuilder.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Module 4

Background; The Life Cycle of a Servlet; Using Tomcat for Servlet Development; A simple Servlet; The Servlet API; The javax.servlet Package; Reading Servlet Parameter; The javax.servlet.http package; Handling HTTP Requests and Responses; Using Cookies; Session Tracking. Java Server Pages (JSP): JSP, JSP Tags, Tomcat, Request String, User Sessions, Cookies, Session Objects.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

The Concept of JDBC; JDBC Driver Types; JDBC Packages; A Brief Overview of the JDBC process; Database Connection; Associating the JDBC/ODBC Bridge with the Database; Statement Objects; ResultSet; Transaction Processing; Metadata, Data types; Exceptions.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Herbert Schildt: JAVA the Complete Reference, 7th/9th Edition, Tata McGraw Hill, 2007.
2. Jim Keogh: J2EE-TheCompleteReference, McGraw Hill, 2007.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Y. Daniel Liang: Introduction to JAVA Programming, 7thEdition, Pearson Education, 2007.
2. Stephanie Bodoff et al: The J2EE Tutorial, 2nd Edition, Pearson Education,2004.
3. Uttam K Roy, Advanced JAVA programming, Oxford University press, 2015.

DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Subject Code	19SEC744	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Provide a strong foundation in database concepts, technology, and practice.
- Practice SQL programming through a variety of database problems.
- Demonstrate the use of concurrency and transactions in database
- Design and build database applications for real world problems.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Identify, analyze and define database objects, enforce integrity constraints on a database using RDBMS.

CO2: Use Structured Query Language (SQL) for database manipulation.

CO3: Design and build simple database systems

CO4: Develop application to interact with databases

MODULE 1

Introduction to Databases: Introduction, Characteristics of database approach, Advantages of using the DBMS approach, History of database applications. Overview of Database Languages and Architectures: Data Models, Schemas, and Instances. Three schema architecture and data independence, database languages, and interfaces, The Database System environment. Conceptual Data Modelling using Entities and Relationships: Entity types, Entity sets, attributes, roles, and structural constraints, Weak entity types, ER diagrams, examples, Specialization and Generalization.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Relational Model: Relational Model Concepts, Relational Model Constraints and relational database schemas, Update operations, transactions, and dealing with constraint violations. Relational Algebra: Unary and Binary relational operations, additional relational operations (aggregate, grouping, etc.) Examples of Queries in relational algebra. Mapping Conceptual Design into a Logical Design: Relational Database Design using ER-to-Relational mapping. SQL: SQL data definition and data types, specifying constraints in SQL, retrieval queries in SQL, INSERT, DELETE, and UPDATE statements in SQL, Additional features of SQL.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

SQL: Advances Queries: More complex SQL retrieval queries, Specifying constraints as assertions and action triggers, Views in SQL, Schema change statements in SQL. Database Application Development: Accessing databases from applications, An introduction to JDBC,

JDBC classes and interfaces, SQLJ, Stored procedures, Case study: The internet Bookshop. Internet Applications: The three-Tier application architecture, The presentation layer, The Middle Tier.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Module 4

Normalization: Database Design Theory – Introduction to Normalization using Functional and Multivalued Dependencies: Informal design guidelines for relation schema, Functional Dependencies, Normal Forms based on Primary Keys, Second and Third Normal Forms, Boyce-Codd Normal Form, Multivalued Dependency and Fourth Normal Form, Join Dependencies and Fifth Normal 10 Hours Form. Normalization Algorithms: Inference Rules, Equivalence, and Minimal Cover, Properties of Relational Decompositions, Algorithms for Relational Database Schema Design, Nulls, Dangling tuples, and alternate Relational Designs, Further discussion of Multivalued dependencies and 4NF, Other dependencies and Normal Forms

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Transaction Processing: Introduction to Transaction Processing, Transaction and System concepts, Desirable properties of Transactions, Characterizing schedules based on recoverability, Characterizing schedules based on Serializability, Transaction support in SQL. Concurrency Control in Databases: Two-phase locking techniques for Concurrency control, Concurrency control based on Timestamp ordering, Multiversion Concurrency control techniques, Validation Concurrency control techniques, Granularity of Data items and Multiple Granularity Locking. Introduction to Database Recovery Protocols: Recovery Concepts, NO-UNDO/REDO recovery based on Deferred update, Recovery techniques based on immediate update, Shadow paging, Database backup and recovery from catastrophic failures.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Fundamentals of Database Systems, Ramez Elmasri and Shamkant B. Navathe, 7th Edition, 2017, Pearson.
2. Database management systems, Ramakrishnan, and Gehrke, 3rd Edition, 2014, McGraw Hill

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Silbers chatzKorth and Sudharshan, Database System Concepts, 6th Edition, McGraw Hill, 2013.
2. Coronel, Morris, and Rob, Database Principles Fundamentals of Design, Implementation and Management, Cengage Learning 2012

INTERNET OF THINGS

Subject Code	19SEC745	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 0(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Assess the genesis and impact of IoT applications, architectures in real world.
- Illustrate diverse methods of deploying smart objects and connect them to network.
- Compare different Application protocols for IoT.
- Infer the role of Data Analytics and Security in IoT.
- Identify sensor technologies for sensing real world entities and understand the role of IoT in various domains of Industry.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Interpret the impact and challenges posed by IoT networks leading to new architectural models.

CO2: Compare and contrast the deployment of smart objects and the technologies to connect them to network.

CO3: Appraise the role of IoT protocols for efficient network communication.

CO4: Elaborate the need for Data Analytics and Security in IoT.

CO5: Illustrate different sensor technologies for sensing real world entities and identify the applications of IoT in Industry.

MODULE 1

What is IoT, Genesis of IoT, IoT and Digitization, IoT Impact, Convergence of IT and IoT, IoT Challenges, IoT Network Architecture and Design, Drivers Behind New Network Architectures, Comparing IoT Architectures, A Simplified IoT Architecture, The Core IoT Functional Stack, IoT Data Management and Compute Stack.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Smart Objects: The “Things” in IoT, Sensors, Actuators, and Smart Objects, Sensor Networks, Connecting Smart Objects, Communications Criteria, IoT Access Technologies.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

IP as the IoT Network Layer, The Business Case for IP, the need for Optimization, Optimizing IP for IoT, Profiles and Compliances, Application Protocols for IoT, The Transport Layer, IoT Application Transport Methods.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Module 4

Data and Analytics for IoT, An Introduction to Data Analytics for IoT, Machine Learning, Big Data Analytics Tools and Technology, Edge Streaming Analytics, Network Analytics, Securing IoT, A Brief History of OT Security, Common Challenges in OT Security, How IT and OT Security Practices and Systems Vary, Formal Risk Analysis Structures: OCTAVE and FAIR, The Phased Application of Security in an Operational Environment.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

IoT Physical Devices and Endpoints - Arduino UNO: Introduction to Arduino, Arduino UNO, Installing the Software, Fundamentals of Arduino Programming. IoT Physical Devices and Endpoints - RaspberryPi: Introduction to RaspberryPi, About the RaspberryPi Board: Hardware Layout, Operating Systems on RaspberryPi, Configuring RaspberryPi, Programming RaspberryPi with Python, Wireless Temperature Monitoring System Using Pi, DS19B20 Temperature Sensor, Connecting Raspberry Pi via SSH, Accessing Temperature from DS19B20 sensors, Remote access to RaspberryPi, Smart and Connected Cities, An IoT Strategy for Smarter Cities, Smart City IoT Architecture, Smart City Security Architecture, Smart City Use-Case Examples.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each. 01 Mark x 10 Questions = 10 Marks

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, choosing at least ONE full question from each module. 08 Marks x 05 Questions = 40 Marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. David Hanes, Gonzalo Salgueiro, Patrick Grossetete, Robert Barton, Jerome Henry, "IoT Fundamentals: Networking Technologies, Protocols, and Use Cases for the Internet of

Things”, 1 st Edition, Pearson Education (Cisco Press Indian Reprint). (ISBN: 978-9386873743)

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Vijay Madiseti and ArshdeepBahga, “Internet of Things (A Hands-on-Approach)”, 1 st Edition, VPT, 2014. (ISBN: 978-8173719547)

DATA COMMUNICATION LAB

Subject Code	19SECL75	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	1 (T) + 2(L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This laboratory course enables students to get practical experience in

- Radiation pattern of antennas.
- Determining gain and directivity of a given antenna.
- Working of Klystron source.
- S-parameters of some microwave passive devices.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On the completion of this laboratory course, the students will be able to:

CO1: Plot the radiation pattern of some antennas using Matlab and wave guide setup

CO2: Obtain the S-parameters of Magic tee and directional couplers.

CO3: Test the IC CD4051 for modulation techniques.

CO4: Study multiplexing techniques using OFC kit.

Description:

NOTE: Experiments can be done using Hardware tools such as Spectrum analyzers, Signal sources, Power Supplies, Oscilloscopes, High frequency signal sources, Fiber optic kits, Microwave measurement benches, DSP processor kit, FPGA kit, Logic analyzers, PC setups, etc. Software tools-based experiments can be done using, FEKO or equivalent open-source simulator, MATLAB etc.

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS:

1. Matlab/C implementation to obtain the radiation pattern of an antenna.
2. Study of radiation pattern of different antennas.
3. Determine the directivity and gains of Horn/ Yagi/ dipole/ Parabolic antennas.
4. Impedance measurements of Horn/Yagi/dipole/Parabolic antennas.
5. Study of radiation pattern of E & H plane horns.
6. Significance of Pocklington's integral equation.
7. Study of digital modulation techniques using CD4051 IC.
8. Conduct an experiment for Voice and data multiplexing using optical fiber.
9. Determination of the modes transit time, electronic timing range and sensitivity of Klystron source.
10. Determination of VI characteristics of GUNN diode, and measurement of guide wave length, frequency, and VSWR (a) SISO (b) SIPO (c) PISO (d) PIPO.

Text Book:**CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD**

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 marks (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	5
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

- Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination.
Experiment 1: 20 Marks (Initial write up: 5 Marks + Execution of Program :10 Marks + Result: 5 Marks)
- **Experiment 2: 20 Marks** (Initial write up: 5 Marks + Execution of Program :10 Marks + Result: 5 Marks)
- **Viva:10 Marks**
- Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks.)

TEXT BOOK:

1. Antenna Design, Balanis, 2nd Ed. PHI Learning Private Limited.

POWER ELECTRONICS LAB

Subject Code	19SECL76	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	1 (T) + 2(L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	42	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

- Study SCR Circuits.
- MOSFET and IGBT
- UJT Relaxation Oscillator.
- Study Controlled Rectifiers
- Study of Speed Control of Stepper and DC Motors

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Define Characteristics SCR Circuits.

CO2: Define Characteristics of MOSFET and IGBT

CO3: Design UJT Relaxation Oscillator.

CO4: Design Controlled Rectifiers

CO5: Design circuits for Speed Control of Stepper and DC Motors

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS:

1. Static characteristics of SCR.
2. Static characteristics of MOSFET and IGBT.
3. SCR turn-on circuit using synchronized UJT relaxation oscillator.
4. SCR Digital triggering circuit for a single-phase controlled rectifier ORA.C. voltage controller.
5. Single-phase full-wave rectifier with R and R-L loads.
6. A.C. voltage controller using TRIAC and diac combination connected to R and R-L loads.
7. Speed control of a separately excited D.C. motor using an IGBT or MOSFET chopper.
8. Speed control of a stepper motor.
9. Speed control of a universal motor and a single-phase induction motor using A.C. voltage controller.
10. MOSFET OR IGBT based single-phase full-bridge inverter connected to R load.

NOTE: At least 5 Experiments are to be simulated by using Suitable Open-Source simulator.

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini –Project / Solving Challenging Problems	Regular mode of Assessment	10
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 2 marks (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment	20
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	5
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

- Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination.
Experiment 1: 20 Marks (Initial write up: 5 Marks + Execution of Program :10 Marks + Result: 5 Marks)
- **Experiment 2: 20 Marks** (Initial write up: 5 Marks + Execution of Program :10 Marks + Result: 5 Marks)
- **Viva:10 Marks**
- Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks.)

PROJECT PHASE I

Subject Code	19SECL77	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2(L) + 2(S)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	-	Total Marks	100
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

- Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected project topic.
- Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
- Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilizing a systems approach.
- Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral form.
- Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Present the seminar on the selected topic orally and/or through power point slides.

CO2: Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.

CO3: Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.

CO4: The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

CO5: Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

INSTRUCTIONS:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey/ visit industries to finalize the topic of the Project. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected project, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the project work

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION:

CIE marks for the project report and seminar shall be awarded (based on the quality of report and presentation skill, participation in the question-and-answer session by the student) by the committee constituted for the purpose by the Head of the Department. The committee shall consist of two faculties from the department with the senior most acting as the Chairman.

Distribution of the Marks:

IA Mark: 50 Marks (Evaluation of the work 20 + Demonstration 15 + Report 15)

External Exam: 50 Marks

Total: 100 Marks

ESEP – MOOC

Subject Code	19SEC78	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	0 (L) + 2(S)	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	-	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To improve learnability
- Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study
- Skill development
- Industry readiness
- Increased confidence level

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: Improve learnability

CO2: Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study

CO3: Develop the skill

CO4: Industry ready

CO5: Have more confidence level

ABOUT THE COURSE:

- A common Online MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is offered in Blended mode.
- The MOOC Coordinator will recommend a department specific common course in MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA to all the students of the batch.
- The assessment will be taken by the MOOC Coordinator for 25 Marks at the end of the Course and the remaining 25 marks will be awarded for the Course Completion.
- The student must attend all continuous assessment taken by the MOOC/COURSERA Course Faculty.

ASSESSMENT METHOD FOR MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA COURSE:

- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course has to recommend a common course for the students to register the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for a Specific Title.
- The students have to take all continuous assessment as recommended by the Course Faculty in the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for the internal assessment of 25 Marks.
- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is responsible to conduct Assessment (MCQs) for 25 Marks in the Internal Assessment of 50 Marks.

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Weight-age	Marks
1	Continuous Assessment taken by the MOOC/Coursera Course Faculty	50	25
2	MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Faculty Coordinator has to Conduct Assessment (MCQs / Assignments)	50	25
Total			50

ESEP: PATENT FILING & IPR

Subject Code	19SQA79	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2 (L) + 0(S)	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	30	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-
Mode of Delivery	RM		

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To introduce fundamental aspects of Intellectual property Rights to students who are going to play a major role in development and management of innovative projects in industries.
- To disseminate knowledge on patents, patent regime in India and abroad and registration aspects
- To disseminate knowledge on copyrights and its related rights and registration aspects
- To disseminate knowledge on trademarks and registration aspects
- To disseminate knowledge on Design, Geographical Indication (GI), Plant Variety and Layout Design Protection and their registration aspects
- To aware about current trends in IPR and Govt. steps in fostering IPR

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to:

CO1: The students once they complete their academic projects, shall get an adequate knowledge on patent and copyright for their innovative research works

CO2: During their research career, information in patent documents provide useful insight on novelty of their idea from state-of-the art search. This provides further way for developing their idea or innovations

CO3: Pave the way for the students to catch up Intellectual Property (IP) as a career option

- R&D IP Counsel
- Government Jobs – Patent Examiner
- Private Jobs
- Patent agent and Trademark agent
- Entrepreneur

MODULE 1

Overview of Intellectual Property: Introduction and the need for intellectual property right (IPR) - Kinds of Intellectual Property Rights: Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Design, Geographical Indication, Plant Varieties and Layout Design – Genetic Resources and Traditional Knowledge – Trade Secret - IPR in India : Genesis and development – IPR in abroad - Major International Instruments concerning Intellectual Property Rights: Paris Convention, 1883, the Berne Convention, 1886, the Universal Copyright Convention, 1952, the WIPO Convention, 1967, the Patent Co-operation Treaty, 1970, the TRIPS Agreement, 1994

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

6 Hours

MODULE 2

Patents - Elements of Patentability: Novelty, Non-Obviousness (Inventive Steps), Industrial Application - Non - Patentable Subject Matter - Registration Procedure, Rights and Duties of Patentee, Assignment and license, Restoration of lapsed Patents, Surrender and Revocation of Patents, Infringement, Remedies & Penalties – Patent office and Appellate Board

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

6 Hours

MODULE 3

Copyrights: Nature of Copyright - Subject matter of copyright: original literary, dramatic, musical, artistic works; cinematograph films and sound recordings - Registration Procedure, Term of protection, Ownership of copyright, Assignment and licence of copyright - Infringement, Remedies & Penalties – Related Rights - Distinction between related rights and copyrights

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

6 Hours

MODULE 4

Concept of Trademarks - Different kinds of marks (brand names, logos, signatures, symbols, well known marks, certification marks and service marks) - Non-Registrable Trademarks - Registration of Trademarks - Rights of holder and assignment and licensing of marks - Infringement, Remedies & Penalties - Trademarks registry and appellate board Design: meaning and concept of novel and original - Procedure for registration, effect of registration and term of protection

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

6 Hours

MODULE 5

Purposes and techniques of Patent searching, Art of Drafting, Anatomy of Patent applications. Overall procedure

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

6 Hours

CONTINUOUS INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (CIA) METHOD

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project/Solving Challenging Problems/Case Study	Regular mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics (group of size 2)/individual)	Regular mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ at the end of each module	2 marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	5
Total			50

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Nithyananda, K V. (2019). Intellectual Property Rights: Protection and Management. India, IN: Cengage Learning India Private Limited.
2. Neeraj, P., & Khusdeep, D. (2014). Intellectual Property Rights. India, IN: PHI learning Private Limited.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Subramanian, N., & Sundararaman, M. (2018). Intellectual Property Rights – An Overview. Retrieved from <http://www.bdu.ac.in/cells/ipr/docs/ipr-eng-ebook.pdf>
2. World Intellectual Property Organisation. (2004). WIPO Intellectual property Handbook.

TECHNICAL SEMINAR

Subject Code	19SEC81	IA Marks	100
Self-study Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	-
Credits	02		

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

- Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected Seminar topic.
- Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
- Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilizing a systems approach.
- Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral form.
- Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a faculty, is required to:

- Present the seminar on the selected topic orally and/or through power point slides.
- Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.
- Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.
- The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.
- Demonstrate the seminar with sound technical knowledge and communication skills

INSTRUCTIONS:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey/ visit industries to finalize the topic of the Seminar. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected Seminar, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the Seminar work

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION:

CIE marks for the seminar report shall be awarded (based on the quality of report and presentation skill, participation in the question-and-answer session by the student) by the committee constituted for the purpose by the Head of the Department. The committee shall consist of two faculty from the department with the senior most acting as the Chairman.

INTERNSHIP

Subject Code	19SEC82	IA Marks	50
Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	50
Credits	3		

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their internship area / topic.
- Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
- Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilizing a systems approach.
- Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral form.
- Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a faculty, is required to:

- Present the work done in his/her internship on the selected topic orally and/or through power point slides.
- Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.
- Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.
- The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.
- Demonstrate the presentation with sound technical knowledge and communication skills

INSTRUCTIONS:

Following are the guidelines to be followed for the Internship Programme:

1. The Internship Programme duration is of Four weeks.
2. The internship can be carried out in any industry / R and D Organization / Research Institute / Educational institute of repute.
3. The institutions may also suggest the students to enroll for the Internshala platform for free internships as there is MoU with the AICTE for the beneficial of the affiliated Institutions (<https://internshala.com/>)
4. The Examination of Internship will be carried out in line with the University Project Viva-Voce examination.
5. The Department/college shall nominate staff member/s to facilitate, guide and supervise students under internship.
6. The students shall report the progress of the internship to the guide in regular intervals and seek his/her advice.
7. After the completion of Internship, students shall submit a report with completion and attendance certificates to the Head of the Department with the approval of both internal and external guides.
8. There will be 50 marks for CIE (Seminar: 25, Internship report: 25) and 50 marks for Viva - Voce conducted during SEE. The minimum requirement of CIE marks shall be 50% of the maximum marks.
9. The internal guide shall award the marks for seminar and internship report after evaluation. He/she will also be the internal examiner for Viva-Voce conducted during SEE.

10. The external guide from the industry shall be an examiner for the viva voce on Internship. Viva-Voce on internship shall be conducted at the college and the date of Viva-Voce shall be fixed in consultation with the external Guide. The Examiners shall jointly award the Viva- Voce marks.
11. In case the external Guide expresses his inability to conduct viva voce, the Chief Superintendent of the institution shall appoint a senior faculty of the Department to conduct viva-voce along with the internal guide. The same shall be informed in writing to the concerned Chairperson, Board of Examiners (BOE).
12. The students are permitted to carry out the internship anywhere in India or abroad. The University will not provide any kind of financial assistance to any student for carrying out the Internship.

PROJECT WORK (WITH OPTION OF PATENT APPLICATION)

Subject Code	19SEC83	IA Marks	100
Practice Hours/Week	24	Exam Marks	100
Credits	13		

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

- Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected project topic.
- Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
- Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilizing a systems approach.
- Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral form.
- Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a faculty, is required to:

- Present the seminar on the selected Project orally and/or through power point slides.
- Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.
- Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.
- The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

INSTRUCTIONS:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey/ visit industries to finalize the topic of the Seminar. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected Seminar, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the Seminar work

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION:

CIE marks for the project report and seminar shall be awarded (based on the quality of report and presentation skill, participation in the question-and-answer session by the student) by the committee constituted for the purpose by the Head of the Department. The committee shall consist of two faculty from the department with the senior most acting as the Chairman.

Distribution of the Marks:

IA Mark: 100 Marks (Evaluation of the work 40 + Demonstration 30 + Report 30)

External Exam: 100 Marks

Total: 200 Marks

Guide: 40%

Internal: 30%

Final Review: 20%

Publication: 10% (Scopus indexed/TR indexed journal)

Evaluation by the Guide (50 Marks):

Self-Motivation and Determination – 10 marks

Working within a Team – 10 marks

Regularity – 10 marks

Technical Knowledge and Awareness related to the Project – 20 marks

Project Report Evaluation (50 Marks):

Project Report – 20 marks

Description of Concepts and Technical Details – 10 marks

Conclusion and Discussion – 10 marks

Journal Publication – 10 marks

External Project Evaluation: 100 Marks (SEE)